

SATISFACTORY

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AA	Autonomous Activities
AIMMS	An Integrated Maintenance Management System
AM	Autonomous Maintenance
AR	Augmented Reality
AS	After Sales
BOM	Bill of Materials
BSC	Business Scenario
CC	Customer Care
CD	Cost Deployment
CIDEM	Common Information Data Exchange Model
DM	Device Manager
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
EEM	Early Equipment Management
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EHS	Environment, Health & Safety
EU	European Union
IoT	Internet of Things
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HR	Human Resources
LM	Localization Manager
MES	Manufacturing Execution System

ML	Manufacturing Leader
NVAA	Non Value Added Activities
OBS	Organizational Breakdown Structure
OM	Ontology Manager
OP	Operating Procedure
OPL	One Point Lesson
ORS	Object Recognition Server
OSF	Open Semantic Framework
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PC	Project Coordinator
PDEC	Plant Data Exchange Component
PPE	Personal Protection Equipment
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
SA	Safety
SFO	SatisFactory Ontology
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSN	Smart Sensors Network
TL	Technical Leader
TQM	Total Quality Management
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UWB	Ultra-Wide Band
VM	Virtual Machine

VoC	Voice of Customer
VoIP	Voice over IP
VR	Virtual Reality
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WCM	World Class Manufacturing
WO	Work Order
WO	WorkPlace Organization
WP	WorkPackage
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a Deliverable of SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under Its Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (H2020).

After diving into SatisFactory lab pre-pilots tackled into Deliverable D5.3 Industrial lab use case Set-up and Demonstration, readers will just have the stunning opportunity to see SatisFactory on action into two real industrial ShopFloors, COMAU's and SUNLIGHT's.

Objective, goal and target of this pamphlet is flanking and accompanying the reader through a challenging journey started when SatisFactory entered the two premises, restoring process-compliant conditions, analysing as-is situation, helping the birth of implied requirements through and users observation and involvement, as best deservers of design guidelines to improve their own working and personal lives (accordingly to Design Thinking and World Class Manufacturing cooperative principles).

The travel into the fantastic world of these two companies, awarded the possibility of joining this prestigious, compelling and captivating European project, proceeds with the presentation of how new technologies, adopted by SatisFactory, can respond to this wishlist, a sort of consumerization of business applications.

Readers will then be brought from design blueprints to reality, being provided with the opportunity of enjoying and touch with bare hands the wonders SatisFactory brought on site.

Is the journey finished? Not at all, definitely. The journey of continuous improvement would never end: a step has been left in the door to allow for last project months further improvements – presented into this paperwork to the readers – that will anyway be just a starting point for future exploitation and dissemination.

1. INTRODUCTION

The issuing of this Deliverable document will be managed in two steps. A first iteration (D5.4.1) of the document will on one side present environmental condition into industrial ShopFloors (COMAU and SUNLIGHT) and relevant selected areas involved by the application of SatisFactory solutions and used as source for such solutions themselves; on the other side, already lead implementations will be exploded, altogether with a planning (scheduling) for next activities. Furthermore, benefits achieved thanks to such implementations and benefits expected from further implementations are assessed and summarized too. If collection and valorisation of gains is crucial to determine project value, lessons learned capitalization is perhaps even more important, in order to establish improvement trends for further exploitation and dissemination of results. Also these enhancements are taken into account both as already planned activities and as nice to have for SatisFactory products lifecycle.

The second document wave will instead include: implementations and deployments due between M30 and M36, gap analysis with respect to “as-planned”, and – again – benefits and lessons learned assessment.

Furthermore, since whole SatisFactory project is focused on the Voice of Customer (VoC), meaning with “customer” all people working inside or around industrial ShopFloors, D5.4 (both D5.4.1 and especially D5.4.2), will deal with feedbacks from the field too. Even if dedicated WorkPackages and Deliverables will deal specifically with collecting, analysing and evaluating such returns from final users or anyway roles which will indirectly benefit from implementations (supervisors, managers and trainers), this feedback will be fed forward to further developments.

Present document structure will be split in two main parts, each of them devoted to one of the two industrial, validating partners, COMAU and SUNLIGHT respectively. Each section will start with a general introduction and description of as-is (as-was actually) ShopFloor environmental condition, with a short summary of needs and potential improvements, that have been already collected and exploited for requirements definition, well described and detailed into three iterations of Deliverable D1.1 – User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines. Interested readers are kindly recommended to tackle the reading of such important handwriting to better understand and appreciate what follows. Anyway, the main idea of these descriptions is to equip kind readers with all needed tools to frame implementations description into business reality of involved industrial partners.

Devoted to this purpose are Chapters 2.1 for what concerns COMAU and 3.1, plus relevant subchapters per each of them.

Furthermore, all preventive activities done at ShopFloor or organizational level in order to prepare the field for SatisFactory implementations are described in these chapters.

After the presentation of environmental conditions and requirements, remaining paragraphs address each a specific Use Case, comparing emerging needs vs developed / implemented SatisFactory modules vs expected and / or achieved goals plus benefits.

In these and following chapters, the two industrial partners sections are not precisely mirrored; i.e. the structure diverges a bit.

COMAU-related section, i.e. **Chapter 2**, and relevant subchapters, is indeed more focused on “foreground” applications; the term foreground applications refers to software tools presenting a user-friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI), workers (Process Operators, Maintenance Technicians, Supervisors, Managers, ...) can interact with, in order to improve their working experience in a captivating way, increasing at the same time both effectiveness / efficiency and job attractiveness (ergonomics, gamification, use of top-edge technologies, mnemonic supports, ...).

Obviously, foreground, usable graphic interface related applications would not work properly or communicate one another and altogether, without the essential presence of “background” SatisFactory software solutions, like LinkSmart Middleware or CIDEM. The fact that some of these background services have not been further detailed into COMAU devoted chapters, would not mean that they deserve a lower importance or that they have not been implemented on COMAU premises. A rich and complete analysis has been delegated to SUNLIGHT paragraphs (**Chapter 3**).

So, **Chapter 2.1.1**, tells the story of SatisFactory software modules and hardware solutions already employed directly supporting people working in the assembly activities of COMAU robot components, giving Them a practical support during training activities to acquire proper skills and become independent on the WorkPlace, or directly in production whether needed; such components will at the same time provide supervisors with real-time monitoring capabilities, and process engineers with powerful instruments for process, procedures and flow management.

Paragraph 2.1.2, will instead surf a rapid overview of key drivers leading next months implementations toward the completion of a remote support for COMAU technician fleet, tirelessly working to maintain and improve COMAU products / solutions value during their entire life cycles.

Finally, a step has been put into these two chapters door, to allow for further developments and deployments, which will enhance SatisFactory project value and that will then be somehow scheduled into **Paragraph 2.3**.

Confirming this COMAU focus toward customer, i.e. workers, the fact that last paragraph of its section is devoted to actors involved both in collection of requirements and in validation process already lead / to be performed in following steps as scheduled and explained into **Paragraph 2.3**.

SUNLIGHT-devoted chapters instead, more analytically address all SatisFactory components in a just fine process oriented way, replicating for each of the four Business Scenarios (BSCs) same structure:

- Context presentation;
- SatisFactory deployment scheduling (requirements collection and design, implementation, site preparation, hardware & software on site installation, commissioning, test, validation and handover in production);
- Process flowchart short description;
- Process flowchart explosion by step and presentation of issues that should be / have been addressed;

- Introduction of SatisFactory modules selected, of which steps and improvement points they address and how they tackle them, with relevant outcome and benefit.

2. COMAU USE CASES

2.1 BUSINESS SCENARIOS

2.1.1 BSC 1.1 Robot Wrist Assembly

COMAU ShopFloor and COMAU Customer premises landscapes are strongly characterized by an overall sense of cooperation and friendliness on WorkPlaces; brand new grey robots started to be produced, instead of historical red ones, that were addressing people attention signalling them warning. Grey represents instead the idea of a user-friendly automation, promoting human – machine cooperation.

Here below (**Image 1**) one picture of new, grey version of COMAU “NJ 110 / 130”, whose wrist assembly process has been taken into account into BSC1.1.

Image 1 – COMAU NJ 110 / 130 in new, grey outfit

Lot of efforts in COMAU have been undertaken to reveal the beauty of automation throughout a transparent showcase.

COMAU believes in intelligence, cooperation and agility at ShopFloor Automation level.

This is the vision beyond AURA – Advanced Use Robotic Arm – an innovative solution making real cooperation between COMAU high payload robots (60 and 110 kg, the highest payloads on the market) and man happens. AURA has been already demonstrated in applications to luxury brands Final Assembly processes.

AURA combines, perception and predictive systems: AURA robots are powered by a special covering, equipped with sensitive areas which can simultaneously perceive the proximity and the contact with a person, or any other automation component, allowing for M2M communication and interoperability. Moreover, auto-adaptability of the system is ensured by AURA ability to modify robot trajectory accordingly to a contact. User experience is

empowered by an integrated vision system which enables AURA robots to predict the movements of people it is interacting with, into area of action.

Image 2 – COMAU AURA (Advanced Use Robotic Arm)

Another best innovation practice is represented by COMAU Amico, a humanoid robot, hinting at cooperation between machines and, increasingly, between man and machine, ensuring precision and effectiveness. Furthermore, Amico wears sensors making its “hand” effectors (grippers) – rather than end effectors – capable of self-adjusting their grasp.

Image 3: COMAU Amico at EMO MILANO 2015 Fair

One of the main drivers characterizing the trend of future COMAU internal or sold-to-customer WorkPlaces is the de-physicalization of stations. This topic addresses the interaction among value chain, i.e. automation, manual operations and logistics with companies human capital.

As per today, WorkPlaces and industrial automation are restricted to specific, closed areas, usually physically delimited by fences, preventing any interfacing of men despite throughout decoupling points such as HMIs that, for their own nature are fixed and un-flexible. Automation is perceived as a closed and closing-out system, even dangerous.

COMAU believes into its technical history and in enabling Customer all over the world glancing and glaring to the beauty of innovation and automation through a transparent

showcase, making things effective and simple. People should look through a friendly automation as in a clear window.

This postulate states the intents of COMAU HuManufacturing, embodied by new machine concepts.

Image 4 – COMAU transparent SmartRob (robotized assembly station), at EMO MILANO 2015 Fair

Removing fences and barriers opens up automation doors, making each inch of a ShopFloor the stage of human beings and machines cooperation, ensuring better logistic flows and increasing exponentially value density.

Furthermore, de-physicalization of stations means also making easy the possibility of accessing and enriching automation “communications”.

Finally the static nature of interfaces needs to be addressed. HMI should be turned off from Human Machine Interface into Human Mobile Interface, i.e. an interaction point that should move altogether with people experiencing the ShopFloor, improving ergonomics, avoiding redundant and Non Value Added Activities (NVAA) and adapting its responses in an intelligent way to human use cases rather than vice-versa. Implementing an interface capable of recognizing people. An interface meant to guide safely human through collaborative automation.

Mechanical assembly of COMAU Robotics products just described, is performed completely internally. As stated above, BSC 1.1 deals with assembly process for COMAU NJ 110 / 130 robots family traditional wrist.

Industrial robots like COMAU ones, are made up by one mechanical structure (mechanical chain, sensors and actuators) and a control unit governing robot movements (see **Image 5** below, while for mechanical structure, please refer to **Image 1** at the beginning of this chapter).

Image 5 – COMAU 5th generation robots controller, C5G

Industrial robot mechanical chain is made up by links, i.e. stiff physical components connected one each other by joint, granting instead robot degrees of freedom.

First three links in a robot constitute its basic structure, determining robot position and used to characterize and classify robot in manipulator types, depending on three joints used to connect the links. Robots can be indeed:

- Cartesian Manipulators;
- Portal Manipulators;
- Cylindrical Manipulators;
- Spherical (Polar) Manipulators;
- SCARA Manipulators;
- Anthropomorphic (Articulated) Manipulators.

Even though COMAU recently started production of new generation, modular SCARA robots (COMAU Rebel-S Family, see **Image 6**), other COMAU robots belong to last cluster listed above. COMAU NJ 110 / 130 is indeed an anthropomorphic articulated robot.

Image 6 – COMAU Rebel-S Robot Family

Industrial anthropomorphic articulated robot is usually made up by six links and relevant six joints, allowing for movement accordingly to six axes. Some robots can then be equipped

with additional axes, usually installed prior to first link – robot “Base” – like turning tables and linear slides, or on the tool – robot “End Effector” – connected to last link, i.e. robot “Flange”.

Anyway, last three robot links, into six-axes configuration, constitute the so-called robot “Wrist”, ensuring orientation degrees of freedom to the end effector.

NJ 110 / 130 robot wrist taken under consideration into BSC 1.1 is indeed comprehensive of part of fourth robot link (gearbox), fifth swinging link and the flange, plus fifth and sixth joints / axes.

Fig. 3A

Image 7 – Industrial, anthropomorphic robot mechanical chain schema³

Image 8 – COMAU NJ 110 / 130 complete robot wrist on online assembly support / tool

³ <http://patentimages.storage.googleapis.com/US8745789B2/US08745789-20140610-D00006.png>

Traditional wrist assembly WorkPlace consists of a mainly manual work station where COMAU operators perform specific operations sequences, which must be strictly followed in order to ensure performances and high reliability level characterizing COMAU products.

Complete manufacturing process includes operations that can fairly be clustered into:

- Components preparation, such as cleaning of metal parts coming from foundry / machining processes or special treatments of mechanical materials (heating, greasing, ...).
- Assembly of Bill of Materials (BOM) components, comprehensive of metal covers, gears, bearings, spacers, gaskets, electrical motors...
COMAU NJ 110 / 130 robot wrists easily contains more than 60 different part numbers! This means a huge amount of components, due to the fact that same part number can be required in a quantity greater than 1 for the assembly of a single wrist. Assembly activities can be grouped into adhesive bonding / sealing (involving different chemical products), insertion / planting (assembly per mechanical interference) and screwing.
- Dressing-up, i.e. application of consumables, like piping and wiring or grease and oil filling.
- Traceability activities ranging from recognition and recording of quality critical components serial numbers (barcodes, ...), to part identification, i.e. tagging of wiring and piping or metal parts marking.
- Static testing of tolerances and mechanical couplings.

Operations onto wrist assembly WorkPlace are performed mainly manually by Process Operators, using manual or at least semi-automatic assembly and testing tools. Process Operators are specialized workers with mechatronics skill, responsible for tools and equipment assembly plus production systems building, with tasks ranging from the assembly of single components to the full integrated system deployment and commissioning. Process Operators may be specialized in one or more of following competence areas:

- Mechanical assembly;
- Electrical wiring;
- Fluidics / Pneumatics piping;
- Preliminary and final testing;
- Troubleshooting (Methodists);
- Support to Commissioning, i.e. power-up and final delivery to customer.

Image 9 – Process Operators during piping installation on a robot arm

Traceability tasks (both of assembled part data like serial numbers and of undergone measurements) are instead performed actually in an hybrid way, where paper printed register forms have not yet been “de-materialized” but are still kept as a support, and measuring equipment are both digital and manual.

Here below just a recap of requirements originating from above described WorkPlace condition, extracted from different iterations of Deliverable D1.1 of SatisFactory project.

Req #	Key	Summary
1	SAFA-4	The HMIs of the platform shall be attractive and easy to use
2	SAFA-13	The tools and applications must be 24/7 operational
3	SAFA-17	The tools shall be able to successfully exchange data with the existing infrastructure at the shop floors
6	SAFA-24	SatisFactory components must have a successful and continuous data exchange with CIDEM
8	SAFA-31	Successful integration of all heterogeneous devices of the shop floors
11	SAFA-34	The system shall be able to monitoring actors through privacy preserving sensors
12	SAFA-37	The platform should present training procedures through multimedia content
14	SAFA-41	All shop floor data must be stored in a common database
16	SAFA-58	The AR components of SatisFactory must have continuous access to the database
17	SAFA-59	The platform shall support social communication between actors
18	SAFA-62	Gamification tools will be interactive with the actors
19	SAFA-65	AR tools will have the ability to interpret the displaying operating procedures

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20	SAFA-66	Multi-Layered Description of Operating Procedures (OP-MLD) Real-time Ready
21	SAFA-67	The platform will allow uncoupling of Multi-Layered Description of operating procedures and their Interactive Real-time Visualization
22	SAFA-69	The symbols/terminology of the data presented on the glasses must be effective and easy to understand
23	SAFA-73	Continuous and successful data transfer between glasses and the database of each shop floor
24	SAFA-75	The frame of the glasses shall be optimal for the workers
27	SAFA-93	Alarms shall be accompanied with a description
28	SAFA-101	Different opinions shall be exchanged during the operation of a task
39	SAFA-105	The system shall provide means of submitting suggestions for improvements available, in order to contribute to modernization and overall improvement of working conditions
34	SAFA-120	The communication product shall be open for non-work-related content
35	SAFA-131	Competition shall be informal and friendly
36	SAFA-132	The product shall not restrict workers' autonomy
39	SAFA-135	The system shall not influence workers' carefulness
40	SAFA-136	The system shall be applicable when workers wear a mask
42	SAFA-140	Support mobile users
43	SAFA-143	Support feedback answers on suggestions for improvement
44	SAFA-146	Release answers/feedback on suggestions for improvements to operators
47	SAFA-154	Continuous access to training procedures
49	SAFA-172	The system shall be able to combine the heterogeneous acquired data from the shop floor
57	SAFA-189	HMI tool (on Mobile device) could be used to take photos from the working area
58	SAFA-192	Association of the workers' names with their suggestions
59	SAFA-193	Time duration availability of the suggestions
60	SAFA-197	UIs shall be in the formal language of the deployment country
61	SAFA-198	All UI interaction parts should be clearly visible
62	SAFA-200	The UIs should be user-friendly
63	SAFA-202	Suggestions will be sorted by submission date

64	SAFA-203	Suggestions filtering support
65	SAFA-204	Personal statistics available to the users
66	SAFA-205	Evaluation of a contribution will support point scale
67	SAFA-206	The product shall keep the prize detail separate from the system
68	SAFA-207	Suggestions system should support suggestion categories
69	SAFA-208	Open suggestions shall be sent to the decision makers
70	SAFA-211	The suggestion submission form shall be in similar format as the pre-existing manual system
71	SAFA-215	Gamification must be presented in several subcomponents of satisfactory
72	SAFA-217	The gamification framework must support PBL
73	SAFA-218	No participant of the gamification shall be exposed as looser
74	SAFA-220	Other SatisFactory components shall submit points of participants to the gamification framework
75	SAFA-221	The gamification framework should allow workers to participate individually as well as in teams
76	SAFA-222	All urgent tasks shall be properly allocated to the employees
80	SAFA-226	All information exchanged and stored within SatisFactory components shall be in a common format understandable from all components
81	SAFA-227	Timely workers notification in case of an alarm
82	SAFA-228	The UI shall provide maps visualization for a more concrete understanding
83	SAFA-229	The messages provided by the system shall be clear and easy to understand
86	SAFA-232	Communication among SatisFactory components will be platform independent

Table 1 – Requirements recap

One important aspect of the manual operations conducted in robot wrists assembly is that both hands are required to perform the operations, thus different presentation tools from tables are required, such as fixed terminals, docking stations or glasses. This aspect led to the modification of following requirements.

Req. #	Key	Summary
36	SAFA-132	The product shall not restrict workers' autonomy
39	SAFA-135	The system shall not influence workers' carefulness

40 SAFA-136 The system shall be applicable when workers wear a mask

Table 2 – Requirements originating from need of keeping Process Operators hands free

The choice of COMAU NJ 110 / 130 robots family traditional wrist assembly WorkPlace, has been performed in order to maximize SatisFactory modules implementation benefit; first of all this work station has been chosen in consideration of its sharply manual nature. Furthermore, it really fits procedural supporting tools, aided by multi-format multimedia contents. Unlike all other WorkPlaces, where several different subgroups are assembled in a variable (random) mix, NJ 110 / 130 wrist assembly is a mono-product area, where same operations are repeated exactly the same way over and over on each part entering the station. Moreover, the complexity of operations and the number of components in the Bill of Material, definitely justify the implementation of some SatisFactory platform components.

Thus, much more attention has been devoted to robot wrist assembly scenario and use case; this lead to the decision of even boosting the impact that the chosen scenario would be invested of; it has been decided to reserve an area into COMAU ShowRoom for an ad-hoc fitted booth, representing the master for a new concept of WorkPlace that would be introduced into COMAU NJ 110 / 130 wrist assembly real workflow and deserves to be spread across the factory and to other potentially interested companies, that can experience it into COMAU ShowRoom.

On such WorkPlace an abstract of complete wrist assembly procedure has been implemented, taking into account just more relevant activities that can be easily shown in public and can catch and draw people attention.

2.1.2 BSC 1.2 Remote Maintenance Support

Initially, a second business scenario (BSC 1.2) regarding COMAU welding gun assembly process / area, was foreseen, that has been discontinued during project execution. Finally a third scenario, regarding internal commissioning of welding lines, has respectively been drafted and then totally distorted. Instead of focusing again on same step of product value-chain, i.e. the “babyness” of automation, the idea has been to move forward throughout COMAU product life-cycle, and to apply SatisFactory principles over maintenance activities, lead – why not but not limited to – over COMAU automated welding lines, and to be then further extended first to other COMAU Automation Systems Business Unit solutions and then to all other Business Units (like Powertrain Machining).

This implied the flanking of other professional profiles to main involved actors and stakeholders, especially the ones related to following COMAU products / lines when their property passes over to customers. This professional family comprehends all people involved in the so-called Customer Care Departments, structured per COMAU Business Unit. Customer Care adepts range from highly-skilled problem-solving technicians, to managerial engineers, to software engineers, other high-profile technical assistance experts (mechanical engineers, ...) and even logistics-related personnel, dealing with spare parts business.

The initially drafted scenario foresaw one maintenance technician receiving a call for intervention based on a task scheduled on Her / His maintenance calendar, automatically generated accordingly to following drivers:

- Automation data / information automatically received from different layer into automation control systems architecture.

This means they can be limited to just mere alarms or they can even be intelligent outputs triggered by certain machine process parameters, elaborated by analytics systems.

Such messages / dispatches should have been somehow enriched by some additional semantic information regarding physical objects involved, cause-effect diagnostics, determining the intervention to be performed, its type, skills needed, tools required to fix it.

- Maintenance technicians' availability in terms of effort assessment.
- Maintenance technicians' professional profiling based on technical skills against required skills for intervention performance.
- Maintenance technicians position inside the ShopFloor (minimum intervention time assessed throughout minimum distance from intervention point calculations achieved through indoor localization systems).

Due to critical reliance of such solution on other systems, in the end the application should be shaped as follows:

- Maintenance technician has to perform a planned maintenance intervention based on Her / His work schedule;
- She / He reaches for intervention target;
- She / He starts a maintenance intervention procedure with multi-format support (markerless Augmented Reality, immersive Virtual Reality, videos, pictures, documentation ranging from PDF manuals to drawings, ...);
- In case of troubles in task execution She / He can ask for a technical support expert starting a call;
- During the call there would be the possibility of sharing pictures bi-directionally, of receiving multi-format documentation on maintenance technician side and, more important, to stream video form ShopFloor to remote support technician;
- On Her / His side technical assistance expert can – in the best case – add information (text or hand-drawn instructions) that will be then real-time displayed on maintenance technician side in Augmented Reality.

No information has been given in the above about digital support used since one of the most compelling challenges would be how to “re-invent” commercial devices, to make them portable, even wearable and to avoid hindering the technician while performing Her / His job. This would mean for example using smart glasses (depending on intervention duration and repeatability / frequency of activity) or even tablets, but imagining how they can be used in an effective way keeping hands free.

2.2 INVOLVED COMPONENTS AND MODULES

2.2.1 Robot Wrist Assembly

Here below, in paragraphs 2.2.1.1 and 2.2.1.2, all Satisfactory modules already implemented and actually used into COMAU ShowRoom demonstrator simulating an abstract of COMAU NJ 110 / 130 traditional wrist assembly process, are listed organized by partner who kindly provided the component itself.

2.2.1.1 REGOLA

Image 10 – BSC 1.1 REGOLA involved modules

In **Image 10** above, a small picture of Satisfactory components Mind Map has been taken, comprehending all modules involved into COMAU BSC 1.1, i.e. traditional robot wrist assembly.

Depicted tools (leaves of the tree), are replicated the same on both branches, Training and In-Factory Platforms; rapidly evolving society is striding toward high turnover and important amount of temporary workers employing.

In this landscape, training deserves key investments. Furthermore, the complexity of assembly and testing operations to be performed, altogether with the high number of components into NJ 110 / 130 wrist Bill of Material and criticality of such operations and traceability tasks to ensure performances and high reliability level characterizing COMAU products, make REGOLA tools a valid alley even into in-process activities.

Following, each component will be exploded and described in details explaining its general purpose / rationale and behaviour, plus the specific opportunities in relation with specific use case.

Creation Tool

Creation Tool is a Windows-based application equipping industrial users with all they would need to digitalize ShopFloor procedures and One Point Lessons (OPL), naturally integrating with factory Manufacturing Execution System (MES), or even partially replacing it at least on procedures creation topic indeed.

Almost every process that can be structured by step can be fed to REGOLA Creation Tool; this dramatically widens the possibilities of implementation in COMAU too. One idea is – for example – extending its coverage to BSC 1.3 on Maintenance Remote Support; maintenance activities, made of parameters check or spare parts replacement in a precise sequence, can be easily inputted to this tool.

Image 11 – Creation Tool, procedures summary page

As per what explained at the beginning of paragraph devoted to REGOLA, Creation Tool gives the possibility of both creating procedures to be used in normal working activities like Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) or One Point Lessons (OPL), supporting people (e.g. but not limited to Process Operators) in Their daily job, or – vice versa – as a valid training platform to get temporary workers or new hired employees (e.g. but not limited to Blue Collars) getting rapidly skilled enough to perform their task autonomously and in quality.

In **Image 11** above, Creation Tool starting page, summarizing all procedures that have been created. Let's see how to create a procedure using – as business case – the simplified abstract of COMAU NJ 110 / 130 robot family traditional wrist assembly procedure implemented to be shown onto COMAU ShowRoom demonstrator.

Image 12 – Creation Tool editing environment, “Procedure” node

When creating a new procedure, a new node is added as father of a Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) like tree. Each procedure is characterized by a unique code and a name and can then be enriched by further information such as:

- Brief description;
- Furtherly detailed description;
- Eventual pre-conditions needed to perform described operations;
- Procedure authors / responsible;
- Procedure aim;
- Procedure versioning number.

An image can be added too, to let users easily figure out procedure scope / output. If the procedure tree is intended as a sort of an enriched Product Breakdown Structure (PBS), a good idea would be using as avatar an image depicting the final product (or Work In Process – WIP) that should be the result of the process. Since current procedure represents a limited deployment of complete one, NJ 110 / 130 wrist has not been used as image; official COMAU logo has been selected instead.

Please note that the environment has been customized accordingly to COMAU colour schemas, i.e. grey shades plus blue pantone, to enhance brand identity. This functionality is accessible through Creation Tool “Settings” tab or even from “Appearance” shortcut.

Image 13 – Creation Tool, setting page

Below “Procedure” node, one or more “Operation” nodes can be added; an operation can be interpreted as a series of activities building up a per se complete and independent mission inside the procedure itself. In this case a unique “Operation” node has been created, comprehending all robot reducer cover pre-assembly Work Packages (WP).

Image 14 – Creation Tool editing environment, “Operation” node

Each node is connected to the flowing by one link associated with one tag describing the type of the relation represented by the link itself. Available link types are:

- **Consecutive.**
When multiple nodes are connected after the same father, consecutive links means that relevant connected nodes should be executed one after the other in a specific and stiff sequence.
- **Contemporary.**
Multiple child-nodes should be executed at the same time, in parallel.
- **Indistinct.**
There is no a fixed cycle-chart, i.e. a prescribed order in which to executed different nodes; this means that nodes suffers of Commutative Property. Changing operands order the result is not changing.
- **Repeated.**
The same link should be passed through multiple (“n”) times.
- **Conditional.**
This is probably the most tricky and interesting relation. The link is undergone just if a specified mathematical condition returns True. In industrial environment this is usually associated with certain process parameters measurement. Such measurement could be either inputted manually by the user (checking with a manual or semi-automatic measuring tool) or directly read from a connected device.

In current, simplistic procedure, just “Consecutive” relations have been used.

Third tier in procedure tree is represented by “Step” nodes. In NJ 110 / 130 wrist assembly demo, three (consecutive) steps have been added, one clustering all “movements”, i.e. activities needed to place the part on the touch point, ready to be worked on, but that are not adding any value to the part itself (and are then called Non Value Added Activities – NVAA), a second step devoted to bearing insertion and the latter to simulated reducer cover closing.

Finally, the fourth procedure tier is made up by “Action” nodes. “Action” nodes can be compared to WBS Tasks since they are atomic unities that cannot be split. Activities can then belong to different clusters, very similar to the one used to classify operations into World Class Manufacturing (WCM) production optimization methodology, mainly employed into identification of losses due to NVAA or un-ergonomic poses. Below a list of activities allowed into REGOLA Creation Tool.

- **Assemble.**
Fix a part on another by different means (mechanical interference, chemical joint, ...).
- **Disassemble.**
Removing a part from a sub-assembly.
- **Act.**
Generic action.
- **Check.**
Visual inspection activities or testing made with other means fall in this cluster.
- **Measure.**
- **Fill in.**
Traceability tasks, meant to register data / information on quality or other purpose.
- **Wait.**
Describe pause status while waiting that a semi-automatic or automatic process is completed (e.g. during thermal treatment of components); can even be used to

indicate a certain pose should be kept for a while (like when gluing two parts altogether).

- Move.
Part manipulation or physical movement of the person performing the tasks of a procedure.

Here below, in **Image 15** a complete branch of entire procedure tree has been followed and shown for demonstration. The step deals with preparation of COMAU NJ 110 / 130 robot family wrist reducer cover, fed to the station, onto so-called offline assembly area.

	Operation			O1
Name:		Reducer cover pre-reassembly		
Description:		Small subset of COMAU NJ 110 / 130 reducer cover assembly activities		
Short Description:		Simulation of reducer cover preparation for assembly on robot wrist		
Pre Conditions:				
	Step			S1
Name:		Reducer cover preparation		
Description:		Subset of activities needed to reference reducer cover		
Short Description:		Preparing reducer cover on offline assembly area		
Pre Conditions:		Reducer cover part availability		
	Action			A1
Type:		Act		
Name:		Reducer cover picking		
Description:		Pick reducer cover CR82341403 from feeding trolley		
Short Description:		Pick wrist cover		
Pre Conditions:				
Repetitions:		1		
	Action			A2
Type:		Assemble		
Name:		Reducer cover referencing		
Description:		Place reducer cover on referencing support centering pins into cover holes		
Short Description:		Place cover on support		
Pre Conditions:				
Repetitions:		1		

Image 15 – COMAU NJ 110 / 130 robot family wrist reducer cover preparation

This tabular view comes from a PDF files generated by REGOLA Creation Tool, export functionality.

Image 16 – Creation Tool, “Action” node details

The gallery reported under tag **Image 16** represents editable details of “Action” nodes, using as paradigm action A2 – Reducer cover referencing described into above procedure branch (**Image 15**). Despite “personal” information (name, code, short and long descriptions, preconditions), that have local destination only, some more input can be fed to “Action” node.

Under “Object” tab, users can associate object involved in the action, to the action itself; objects can be:

- Items, i.e. manipulated parts or anyway components subject of the task.
- Objects to / from. Being an “Assembly” action, this category represent the parts on top of which handled components (the “Items”) should be fixed.
- Objects with; tools needed to perform assembly activity.

Objects inserted so far, will feed Creation Tool “Inventory”, i.e. a complete list of all materials involved in the procedure with relevant quantities and ERP-relevant information (identification code, name and description), plus pictures of objects themselves. This inventory overlaps indeed with procedure Bill of Materials (BOM) and is exportable in PDF format too (altogether with the procedure).

Finally, the “Descriptive Layers” tab, is devoted to attaching pre-existing multi-format materials to the “Action” node. Multimedia files supported range over:

- Text (just typed in a specific form);
- Audio;
- Video;
- 3D animations (that can be shown both in Virtual Reality or even associated with a tag on Augmented Reality visualization purpose);
- Documents.

All resources added to a procedure will be stored in a collection of resources. Creation Tool let users browsing all resources used, both at procedure level only and / or at global level, summarizing up all resources ever used in all procedures created.

Expected execution time values have not been filled in the example above; this is due to the fact that measuring the Cycle Time of manual operations (required for creating a real cycle-chart of Gantt Chart), needs special authorizations from Human Resources Department.

Procedure Server

Briefly, REGOLA Procedure Server is meant for uploading exported procedures on a shared area, so that authorized clients will be able to access to (and download) always up-to-date procedures all over the plant.

Authorized clients are represented, at actual state of the art, by Android mobile devices, equipped with REGOLA Presentation Tool App.

The potential for creating one procedure centrally and deploying it on a distributed and scalable basis, is of crucial interest and importance for global companies, implementing manufacturing worldwide standards to ensure world-class quality; even more relevance is returned by implementation in maintenance field. Maintenance procedures could be created during COMAU machine / equipment design and engineering by System Engineering Department, that can furtherly keep them up to date during whole product life cycle, in a transparent way to utilizers: it will be sufficient to upload updated procedures into shared area (e.g. company cloud in the future); when clients will connect to an enabled network, newest procedure release will be downloaded and shown to technician performing maintenance tasks.

Presentation Tool

REGOLA Presentation Tool is the consumer counterpart of Creation Tool plus Procedure Server side.

Presentation Tool manages user authentication and let authorized users synchronizing with exported procedures sharing area; once downloaded procedures can be used locally, supporting – on actual configuration – COMAU NJ 110 / 130 robot wrist assembly operations. Furthermore, to overcome connectivity issues on ShopFloor due to electromagnetic disturbances and devices conflict on saturated communication channels (especially WiFi 2.4 GHz), Presentation Tool let users exploit procedures benefits even offline, delegating procedure updating to when device connectivity is restored and ensured.

Image 17 – Presentation Tool, main page explanation

Image 17 shows main page Presentation Tool users will display when using Android App on a tablet supporting Her / His working activity.

Into the dark grey bar on the top of the template, the entire branch of procedure tree created with REGOLA Creation Tool is displayed. During procedure execution, the tree is completely navigated accordingly to priority associated with relations connecting procedures nodes. Referring to above mentioned simplified COMAU NJ 110 / 130 robot traditional wrist assembly procedure, where all links have been set as “Consecutive”, Presentation Tool will first display first “Action” of first “Step” of unique “Operation” whose father is the “Procedure” node. Then, all other “Actions” of same “Step” branch will be displayed in order; finally first “Action” in sequence of second “Step” node will be displayed without any interruption, and so on.

Below the navigation pane, a lighter grey box contains the textual description of the action to be performed. Such description is the same that have been inputted into “Textual Descriptive Layer” input box into REGOLA Creation Tool, accessible through the link shown on third thumbnail in images gallery of **Image 16** above. The description can even be listened to through a text to speech service triggered on clicking the red audio button on the right (see **Image 17**).

Body of Presentation Tool page is occupied by all materials (Component, Tool and Equipment) managed throughout Presentation Tool Inventory tab. Details inputted into Presentation Tool Items Inventory enriching each object are displayed on mobile device:

- Picture / Image;

- Object (Component / Tool / Equipment) code (or description), that should be self-explanatory for users;
- Involved quantity, representing quantity of relevant material involved into procedure “Action”.

Finally, page footer is devoted to additional support functions, ancillary to actual procedure “Action” node which should help user into performance of the task. These functionalities should overlap perfectly with REGOLA Creation Tool Descriptive Layers (see **Table 3** legend below), and are – by so – active just in case procedure creator has linked multimedia files to relevant “Action”.

	<p>Settings Allows user accessing App settings</p>
	<p>Text User can access to Textual Descriptive Layer inputted into Creation Tool and summarized into light grey box on top of Presentation Tool main screen (below navigation pane)</p>
	<p>Image Shortcut to images gallery containing pictures linked to procedure “Action” node into Creation Tool – Descriptive Layers These images do not coincide with pictures attached to inventory objects involved into procedure task but usually describe “Action” phases or point on which user should pay particular attention (OPL)</p>
	<p>Video Used to access video tutorials that procedure creator decided to attach to the node into Creation Tool</p>
	<p>Document All kind of document linked into Creation Tool – Descriptive Layers Can range from manuals to mechanical drawings and controls (electrical / pneumatic / hydraulic) schemas This functionality deserves a specific mention and particular attention on maintenance procedures purpose Most times in fact COMAU maintenance technicians would need to access to machine design and engineering documentation when performing their duty</p>
	<p>Audio Audio-guide supporting operators during process execution without needing to draw attention from touch point May (or may not) be limited to text to speech service applied to Textual Descriptive Layer and described shortly above</p>

	<p>Virtual Reality</p> <p>Grant access to a virtual environment where users can navigate a 3D CAD world containing involved object and, potentially, a 3D animation of the same</p>
	<p>Augmented Reality</p> <p>Access to device camera; when user frames referenced AR tag (please consider that REGOLA implements now non-markerless Augment Reality solutions), almost every referenced Descriptive Layer can be displayed overlaid to real world (in a position calculated relatively to reference system associated with AR tag)</p> <p>Most effective applications are the ones displaying 3D animations describing in a detailed way procedure “Action”, on top of real object</p>

Table 3 – Presentation Tool, Descriptive Layers legend

Focusing on COMAU complete procedural branch described into **Image 15** slightly above (into Creation Tool related paragraph), what would be displayed into Presentation Tool is first “Action” A1 – Reducer cover picking; Process Operator would then be able to switch to following activity, i.e. A2 – Reducer cover referencing and, from that, to the first activity of following “Step”.

Please consider anyway that, not overlapping 100% with a Manufacturing Execution System (MES), Presentation Tool will deal neither with traceability nor with quality certification of “Actions” performed by users.

Here below (**Image 18**), an example of REGOLA Presentation Tool applied to second “Action” (A2 – Reducer cover referencing).

Image 18 – Presentation Tool, COMAU application example

This very simple case represent the activity of placing the metal reducer cover on top of offline robot wrist assembly area equipment (referencing support); as described above, into REGOLA Creation Tool paragraph, this “Action” of “Assemble” type requires one “Item”, the handled object – i.e. reducer cover support – and one “Object To / From”, the equipment where the part should be placed – i.e. referencing support. No “Object with”, i.e. tool, is needed. Both involved components / materials have been represented by mean of an image to easily spot them on the WorkPlace, and relevant self-explanatory codes (marked on the parts) are shown, altogether with relevant Bill of Materials (BOM) quantities required (one per component).

Due to the very low complexity of this task, no document or video is required. Process operators can instead access:

- Pictures describing the accurate placing procedure, highlighting which holes of the cover should be used for positioning on support pins;
- Text to speech audio, reading Textual Descriptive Layer;
- 3D animation of the referencing activity, displayed both in Virtual Reality and in Augmented Reality.

Augmented Reality applications into COMAU NJ 110 / 130 robot wrist assembly demonstrator, have been based on simple tags / markers, i.e. easily recognizable pictures taken into COMAU ShopFloor, printed, plasticised (in order to prevent them from mechanical and chemical wear) and applied onto Process Operator WorkPlace (simulated inside COMAU Grugliasco ShowRoom), close to the touchpoint. Into **Image 19** below an example of the tag used for A2 – Reducer cover referencing “Action”.

Image 19 – Example of COMAU AR Tag / Marker to identify offline assembly area

Such markers can be used to accurately identify one object or just to track one area; in both cases, they are used as reference for drawing a reference system that will be used for the 3D placement in space of objects shown in Augmented Reality (3D shapes / animations, writings, images, ...). Their quality and positioning are then of crucial importance.

Image 20 – Presentation Tool, COMAU Virtual Reality example

Image 21 – Presentation Tool, COMAU Augmented Reality Example

Summarizing up, REGOLA Presentation Tool represent a Human Machine Interface (HMI) or, better a Human Mobile Interface, for SatisFactory applications and is by so of crucial importance for COMAU that is investing a lot on renewing interactions among the machine, meant as the whole of automation and manual processes / WorkPlaces, and people.

2.2.1.2 ISMB

Image 22 – BSC 1.1 ISMB involved modules

Image 22 above represents the complete branch and bound tree of ISMB partner modules that have been implemented till now (M28 – May 2017) and are currently in use in COMAU and shown to visitors in COMAU Grugliasco ShowRoom.

To summarize shortly all components presented into the Mind Map, ISMB rich portfolio of solutions can be basically described as a two-sided solution. Locally, on COMAU NJ 110 / 130 robot wrist assembly WorkPlace (or at least on the implemented replica / demonstrator), a hardware platform built-up with:

- Nr. 1 Intel® NUC mini PC;
- Nr. 1 Microsoft Kinect 2 sensor, equipped with both colour and depth cameras;
- Nr. 1 USB Jabra Speak 410 Speakerphone;
- Nr. 1 Generic PC monitor.

Such local architecture is meant for monitoring purposes, whose output is consumed / shown into remote Visualization Toolkit WebApp.

Furthermore, locally, part of the Digital Andon, the Smart Assembly Station Display, has been deployed. Practically, REGOLA Presentation Tool is used for sequential procedure steps display and multi-format support material (in the widest sense possible, comprehensive, but not limited to Augmented and Virtual Reality or videos) access on a mobile basis, but – requiring the usage of a portable device, it keeps Process Operators hands hindered. ISMB Smart Assembly Station Display is meant to improve and increase the

impressive added value of REGOLA Presentation Tool, even though integration of the two modules has not been already completed. Smart Assembly Station Display is indeed accessing to services and functionalities offered by ISMB Gesture & Content Recognition Manager – Hands Free Browsing module. Kinect sensor is installed in the right position to recognize simple gestures Process Operators can perform without moving or even distracting from the touchpoint on the WorkPlace (defining as touchpoint the exact working position where value added activities are aimed) and with no need of handling mobile devices. At the moment Process Operator can just browse among different static steps of a procedure, swiping Her / His right hand right to left to go ahead or vice-versa swiping with left hand, left to right to return to previous step. Potentialities of integration with access to multimedia contents by mean of gestures and especially to Augmented Reality applications implemented on Windows OS should now be the target.

Image 23 – Digital Andon, Smart Assembly Station Display, Instructions Visualization

The basic idea is accessing (automatically or by gesture selection) Augmented Reality procedures when reaching a step which is enriched by such feature, and seeing on ISMB Smart Assembly Station Display the touchpoint, video streamed by mean of a camera, with Augmented Reality instructions / 3D animations on it.

Furthermore ISMB local WorkPlace deployment is enriched by the possibility of starting a support call to an area supervisor or anyway a team responsible / accountable (Technical Leader in COMAU Organizational Breakdown Structure – OBS). Again, the Kinect recognized simple gestures, i.e. it is sufficient that Process Operator raises up Her / His right hand forming, with Her / His other arm, a phone handset shape, to start a support call, whose experience is powered by the USB Jabra speakerphone mentioned at the beginning of this section. The mirrored pose is shaped to terminate the call.

ISMB Visualization Toolkit is instead web application consuming information coming from local implementations. Being a web application it can be accessed through different devices: PCs (desktop / laptop), tablets and smartphones. Preferred support are, anyway, mobile devices since the aim of the App is in fact equipping Process Operators responsible (COMAU Technical Leader) with a monitoring tool that can help Her / Him supervise Her / His people on the move.

The first page displayed to supervisor users is the “Map”, represented into **Image 24** below. On the main white pane, a simplified layout of the ShopFloor is represented. On COMAU application, the ShowRoom map has been used instead. Onto the 2D drawing some “Forbidden Areas” can be defined, and are represented by transparent red rectangles with solid red borders. These areas are identified on the basis of incident probability density; they can be zones where access is forbidden, where human presence over a fixed period of time can be dangerous or just areas where non-collaborative (traditional) automation solutions have been implemented. Latter case is the one closest to COMAU reality; entering a traditional automatic robotized cell requires taking pre-emptive safety countermeasures, and – anyway – people in the area should be notified of human presence inside the machine.

ISMB Localization Manager module, that has not been represented into **Image 22** Mind Map since it has not yet been implemented on COMAU premise, foresee the possibility of localizing Process Operators on the ShopFloor, through and indoor GPS system based on anchor nodes and wearable devices, i.e. wearable sensors that can be embedded e.g. into working clothing, avoiding compromising Personal Protection Equipment (PPE) European safety certification by modifying them. Combination of Localization Manager and definition of forbidden areas into Visualization Toolkit WebApp Map View, will grant the possibility of real time monitoring accesses to danger zones.

Image 24 – Visualization Toolkit WebApp, Map View

Into actual implementation of ISMB suite, the only localization-like feature is instead represented by the Presence Detection module of the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager. Through elaboration of Microsoft Kinect camera acquired video, it is possible to detect indeed when Process Operator reaches for Her / His WorkPlace and stops in working position, discriminating people that are just passing by. Process Operator presence is signalled to Technical Leader (supervisor) through a robot icon overlaid to ShowRoom map; the icon turns bright green when Process Operator is detected onto working area and She / He is ready to start Her / His activities. Furthermore, presence icon persists into its “excited” status for all the time Process Operator remains by Her / His WorkPlace, performing Her / His activities.

Till the icon remains green, COMAU Technical Leader can remotely monitor and supervise Process Operator working conditions; tapping on robot icon itself, a pop-up window opens up with real-time video streaming from Kinect camera installed on top of SatisFactory WorkPlace inside COMAU ShowRoom. Beside video streaming, process / area supervisor can spot:

- PPE integrity. Prior to start its service by the WorkPlace, each Process Operator must be equipped with PPE prescribed by COMAU Environment, health and Safety (EHS) Department for the specific working activity performed (determined by the amount and type of risk workers are exposed to when executing such job).

Video streamed by Kinect camera is elaborated in order to recognize PPE presence and quality (external aesthetic integrity) and a checklist is automatically filled on the video pop-up window, so that supervisor is immediately notified of dangerous conditions.

Mostly used PPE on COMAU ShopFloor are anti-cut gloves against mechanical risks and safety shoes; nevertheless, on demonstrative purpose, onto COMAU ShowRoom demonstrator COMAU high visibility vests and COMAU helmets are currently recognized. This is mainly due to the fact that such PPE, especially the vest, are given to all visitors entering COMAU plant and – by so – potentially visiting COMAU ShowRoom and SatisFactory demonstrator inside it.

- Procedure progresses. This means that – in robot wrist assembly case – Technical Leader can know at any time the exact status (in terms of completion, not qualitative) of Work in Process. This percentage is calculated as the ratio among number of “Actions” already completed by Process Operator on current job (part) and total number of “Actions” foreseen for complete procedure on that specific job. For a more accurate definition of “Action”, please refer to the section devoted to REGOLA procedures Creation Tool into chapter 2.2.1.1 above.

The number of already performed activities is instead calculated through ISMB Gesture & Content Recognition Manager, Hands Free Browsing module. When a process Operator swipes Her / His hands to navigate to next procedural task, it is assumed that previous task has been 100% completed, and so the number of performed “Actions” is incremented by one. In case of error or when a user wants to return back to a previously skipped activity, counter can be “undone”, i.e. Process Operator swipes back to relevant “Action” and completed activities counter is decremented accordingly (minus one per each back-browsing gesture).

Finally on the right of Visualization Toolkit WebApp – Map View:

- Telephone headset icon used to start a call toward the WorkPlace or pick an incoming call up.
- Notification icon that opens up a notification board.

Grey notification pane (**Image 24**) can contain three types of messages.

- Yellow messages, belonging to assistance requests category. When one Process Operator needs for Technical Leader support, She / He can just rise Her / His hands; Kinect camera will recognize the gesture, the robot icon indicator on Map View (**Image 24**) will turn yellow and a proper notification is added, with relevant timestamp, onto the pane.
- Red messages, signalling incidents. When Gesture & Content Recognition Manager, Incident Detection engine detects that a Process Operator falls down to ground rapidly to the ground and stays there still for a few seconds, robot icon turns red and an alarm notification is immediately raised, to spot supervisor attention.
- White messages; this notifications category comprehends all type of information relevant for Technical Leaders. Usually they are displayed after an incident happens, signalling to supervisor that a video of the situation prior to the incident has been captured, altogether with the position (whether known) of all personnel inside the ShopFloor at the moment of the event.

In general, people privacy is anyway preserved nevertheless video media exploiting; first of all, videos are not kept or stored despite in case of incident. Even in these cases anyway, the videos:

- Will only be handled by authorized personnel;
- Are captured and stored by mean of depth camera instead than with colour camera, by so dissimulating people physiognomy.

All saved videos are accessible for replay by authorized personnel throughout “Video” tab into Visualization Toolkit WebApp (**Image 24**).

2.2.2 Remote Maintenance Support

BSC 1.3 – Remote Maintenance Support, suffers less maturity with respect to BSC 1.1 – Robot Wrist Assembly; architectural structure consolidation and implementation activities of selected modules are starting these months.

Anyway, a draft of all technical partners’ modules that could be theoretically involved into the Business Scenario is listed below in **Image 25** Mind Map.

Image 25 – COMAU BSC 1.3, Remote Maintenance Support, potentially involved modules draft

Without going further in details again on single partners modules (please see chapter 2.1.1 and relevant sub-chapters / paragraphs for a fairly long and accurate description), here below just a summary on how fitting each module into the Use Case.

As discoursed there and then in above chapters, REGOLA modules, already implemented on COMAU premise, can easily be used for creation, exportation and usage on the move even of maintenance and not only of manufacturing procedures; by so, Creation Tool, Procedure Server and Presentation Tool have been de facto included into Remote Maintenance Support Usage Scenario.

Procedures will be created by COMAU technical service experts coming from Customer Care Department (and that will then be included into actors involved by SatisFactory project) on COMAU standard products (maybe starting with COMAU robots and C5G control units); procedures will then be published and kept updated on Procedure Server, so that every consumer in the ShopFloor can access them locally by mean of Presentation Tool App.

And here comes a first challenge, i.e. attempting to bring needed information (procedure “Actions” and Descriptive Layers, as they are called into REGOLA Creation Tool and entire suite) to maintenance technicians, without hindering their hands. One first, potential, solution would be to use GLASSUP smart glasses; another idea could be instead (maybe in parallel) trying to re-adapt ISMB Gesture & Content Recognition Manager – Hands Free Browsing module on mobility.

The core implementation of BSC 1.3 is anyway the remote support to maintenance. This can be potentially be performed by use and re-adaptation of actual ISMB Multiple Media Manager functionalities: Live Streaming and Audio Call Management. Furthermore a bilateral architecture should be implemented, having on one side (locally) tools supporting maintenance technicians in their own activities and on the other one the other side (remotely) an assistance / supervision dashboard, recalling ISMB Visualization Toolkit WebApp.

Second huge challenge would be enriching – whether feasible – the Live Streaming functionality, with the possibility for video consumer, i.e. COMAU technical service manager / expert, to “draw” instructions on screen that would be displayed in Augmented Reality on Hands Free Browsing enriched Presentation Tool, exploited by local maintenance technician instead. Remote contents sharing should also include real-time, drag & drop forwarding of multi-format files, belonging to categories already included into REGOLA Creation Tool – Descriptive Layers, i.e. text, audio, video, images, 3D animations and documents (see chapter 2.2.1.1 and relevant subchapters devoted to Creation Tool features presentation).

Nevertheless, regardless the feasibility of this “what You draw is what You see” functionality, local access to procedures throughout a Presentation Tool, must support all Descriptive Layers actually foreseen for BSC 1.1 – Robot Wrist Assembly. This includes e.g., but not limited to, Augmented Reality, both accordingly to REGOLA marker-based algorithms, both with markerless solutions, like the ones REGOLA and CERTH are actually working altogether on (ORS – Object Recognition Server in **Image 25** fairly above), whether portable on a mobile device.

Finally, let’s finish with the beginning of the process! Since the scenario (see chapter 2.1.2 and relevant section into SatisFactory Deliverable D1.1 – third iteration) foresees maintenance personnel executing maintenance activities accordingly to own schedules, some solutions for maintenance calendar creation, management and update (based on intervention result and feedback) – especially for periodic, pre-emptive maintenance interventions – should be included in BSC 1.3 scope.

Partners working on such solutions are ATLANTIS, with its AIMMS application and relevant mobile App for Android OS, and ISMB, with its Work Schedule View package embedded into

Visualization Toolkit WebApp, interfacing different calendars and by so potentially integrating with ATLANTIS solution.

In Mind Map schema shown above (**Image 25**), some more modules of ISMB suite that have not been described so far in this chapter have been mentioned. Some of these modules have indeed been already investigated for BSC1.1 – Robot Wrist Assembly (see paragraph above), the remaining ones will instead be deserved attention and described briefly below.

Nevertheless, the possibility of integrating them into BSC 1.3 overall architecture is still uncertain, mainly due to the fact that they require fixed installations. This both means redundancy of actual / foreseen installations related to BSC 1.1 – Robot Wrist Assembly, and furthermore they just limitedly fit the industrial scenario of maintenance activities, that do not involve limited and well defined spaces, but are natively distributed.

Indoor localization solutions, incident detection and incident video recording / replay services can be of crucial interest indeed for general maintenance activities, especially when such activities are performed during production stop periods or in “dangerous” environment (not easy to access, out of sight / reach). Anyway, implementation of these solutions actually requires a platform made of reference anchor nodes, wearable sensors, Kinect camera and local intelligent node (Intel® NUC or equivalent mini-PC); stated requirements would be in conflict with the mobile nature of maintenance activities and furthermore will require proliferation of installation in COMAU.

Anyway, accordingly to the continuous improvement and iterative approach plus methodology characterizing whole SatisFactory project, further implementation details will be given into second Deliverable iteration, i.e. D5.4.2, due by month M36 (project end milestone).

2.3 GENERAL IMPLEMENTATION SCHEDULING

Accordingly to SatisFactory project general iterative approach and methodology, all further steps required to complete COMAU Use Cases implementation, would be periodically evaluated to check compliance to project roadmap.

Thus, a three major phases macro scheduling has been developed; the first implementation wave has already been started, and is dealing mainly with the completion of actual tools on field related to BSC 1.1 – Robot Wrist Assembly. This is including – among others – ISMB Localization Manager plus Ergonomics module, and all related consumers applications.

The first one consists into installation of four fixed anchor nodes, which should be located at relevant four ends of COMAU ShowRoom; such nodes will be used for real-time, accurate monitoring of Process Operators position inside the area. Anonymizing such data will help improving workers safety on the ShopFloor, alerting supervisors (Technical Leaders) of eventual risky conditions, like – e.g. – unauthorized presence of personnel inside forbidden areas, excessive latency in one position (that can mean both that an incident has happened – that should be signalled by Incident Detection tool too – or that a static posture is being kept for a too long time period, resulting into long-term deterioration of ergonomics and thus health), at the same time preserving people privacy.

Image 26 – Anchor node

Second ISMB module that should be implemented under step 1 is the one regarding ergonomics of Process Operator working postures. The system will consist of ad-hoc developed wearable sensors embedded into workers safety garments, and one system triggering warning alerts or alarms based on Process Operators postures. Due to the fact that people are used to wear high visibility jackets when entering COMAU ShowRoom, where BSC 1.1 demonstrator has been implemented and – by so – Ergonomics module will stay into, such sensors will be embedded into this type of garment, and will be able to monitor trunk bending forward / upward and trunk bending sideways / twisting.

Here below the rules that have currently been set (**Table 4** and **Table 5**), where red colour signals not acceptable working situations and should raise an immediate alarm, while yellow highlights mark warning conditions / positions that should not be kept for more than a certain period or that should not be repeated more than “x” times. Such rules have been inspired by European Norm EN 1005-4: 2009⁴ on human postures in relation to machinery, during machinery assembly, installation, set-up and commissioning, working life, life cycle management and maintenance, plus repair, cleaning, dis-assembly and transportation of machinery itself.

Trunk bending forward	Acceptability		
	Static Position	Movement	
		< 2 times per minute	≥ 2 times per minute
$x < 0^\circ$ (backward bending)	Acceptable if and only if full trunk support is available (e.g. backrest)	Acceptable if and only if full trunk support is available (e.g. backrest)	Not acceptable
$0^\circ \leq x < 20^\circ$	Acceptable	Suggested	Acceptable
$20^\circ \leq x < 60^\circ$	Acceptable only for short duration and with long enough recovery	Acceptable	Not acceptable

⁴ Safety of machinery – Human physical performance – Part 4: Evaluation of working postures and movements in relation to machinery

	periods among iterations		
$X \geq 60^\circ$	Not acceptable	Acceptable only for short duration during working day	Not acceptable

Table 4 – Trunk bending forward / backward thresholds

Trunk bending sideways	Acceptability		
	Static Position	Movement	
		< 2 times per minute	≥ 2 times per minute
$0^\circ \leq x < 10^\circ$ (left or right)	Acceptable	Suggested	Acceptable
$0^\circ \leq x < 20^\circ$	Not acceptable	Acceptable only for short duration during working day	Not acceptable

Table 5 – Trunk bending sideways or twisting thresholds

Anyway, please consider that these thresholds only refer to atomic movements; this means that in case more than one suggested, acceptable or conditionally acceptable are performed into a combined way, it can also be that the resulting complex behavior reduces significantly maximum bending / twisting angles (e.g. in case Process Operator bends and twist Her / His trunk simultaneously). Finally, these rules can even be affected by environmental conditions (permanence in a certain posture, frequency of repetitions, recovery periods and relevant duration, trunk or other body supports provision, PPE and tools utilization, ...) or force application, thus maybe making not acceptable bending / twisting angles that should theoretically be per se even acceptable.

ISMB modules are just an example of the implementations that should be lead during wave 1; other activities can e.g. be REGOLA Presentation Tool integration with ISMB Hands Free Browsing module.

Second and third implementation waves will instead see the commissioning / re-adaptation of modules and tools that would be selected for deployment into BSC 1.3 – Remote Maintenance Support perimeter. Some more complex activities would be obviously spread cross implementation steps, e.g. REGOLA and CERTH ORS – Object Recognition Server. By so, the Gantt Chart depicted below (see **Image 27**) must not be considered as a block schema; each bar represents both an advancement with respect to implementation of contents and as an opportunity to review and improve previous deployments.

Anyway, for further details on implementation scope, refer to all what has been described in details in chapters 2.1.1 and 2.1.2 above.

After each implementation steps a review milestone has been indeed established. Such milestones (M30 and M33) will consist into internal progress status meetings where COMAU accountable would eventually line-up with involved technical partner and especially collect feedback from company end-users which will feed forward further implementation steps.

People working on the ShopFloor are indeed target of SatisFactory project, and – at the same time – definitely best deservers of requirements and design principles for solutions meant to improve both Their personal and working life (basic principles of World Class Manufacturing – WCM, WorkPlace Organization – WO Pillar⁵ and of Design Thinking methodology), motivating Them and Their colleagues to work in today factories.

⁵ World Class Manufacturing can be defined as a complete methodology prescribing rigorous approaches and tools implementation in order to dramatically and continuously improve organizational cultures not only in industrial companies, but in every organization – from personal life and domestic economy to services (e.g. one of WCM implementation benchmarks is the UK Royal Mail brilliant case study).

Accordingly to the methodology itself historical heritage, two souls live inside World Class Manufacturing body, thanks also to main contributors of its corpus of knowledge and theorists. The first stream follows operational excellence principles, aimed to strategically position companies suffering the strains of cost competition in a saturated market, where an excess in Offer requires for price demolition to cheer Demand up. Market diversification and outclassing competitiveness may be achieved with in-process quality aimed to tackle waste and losses (in time, cost and scope, where even occupied space wears the garments of cost) with problem solving competences, increasing production efficiency on one side, and delivering outstanding excellence to customer accordingly to zero errors and zero defects criteria (vertical differentiation).

This line sinks its roots into Total Quality Management (TQM) model, born in Japan during the Fifties and into the Lean Production crusade against disposals (the struggle against contributions not meant to add value to the product, whether physical or not) in Toyota pull system. Anyway such inseparable spirit of the WCM is probability not the one that deserves more interest inside SatisFactory project. The Human part of the methodology is mainly due to the work of Dr. Schonberger, theorist of the professional development of workers through making Them responsible and involving Them, as key factor for working conditions change and strategic positioning of companies.

World Class Manufacturing proposes substantially a holistic approach, where all people of the organization should be involved into the continuous improvement and contribute to the development, increase, capitalization and maintenance of company know-how.

This attention paid to people can be found multiple times inside World Class manufacturing theoretical infrastructure. WCM methodology is, briefly, based on ten managerial pillars building the base on top of which again ten technical pillars sustain WCM temple tympanum. For example, the central role of human capital can be found in first technical pillar, i.e. “Safety” (SA): one company is made of people; therefore it should struggle to ensure zero incidents. Again Human Resources centered approach returns into Autonomous Activities (AA) technical pillar aiming to continuously improve working environment, restoring basic (as-is) conditions, enhancing ergonomics on the WorkPlace (stuff indeed for “WorkPlace Organization” – WO sub-pillar of AA technical pillar) and making workers first responsible for the maintenance and standardization of their working positions (machines or whatsoever), with “Autonomous Maintenance” (AM) subpillar. Probably maximum exemplum of people-centered design of WCM revolution of factory organization is anyway the “People Development” technical pillar.

On managerial pillar side instead, the whole structure is devoted to people; a change in management, communication, dissemination and awareness, common vision and intents, training and motivation, capitalization of lessons learned, planning and scheduling are of crucial importance to make possible the technical path to spread inside the company.

Thanks to “Cost Deployment” technical pillar (CD), Benefit on Cost Ratio (B/C) is another way – maybe simpler but even more metaphoric – to calculate ROI (Return on Investment), not considering money gained times spent, but money that have not been wasted against money spent to avoid this disposal.

Image 27 – Next implementations roadmap

Last project month (M36) has been kept for an activity that has been defined as “Internal Audit”. Again, this means that internal users are main project stakeholders, so that at least one month should be devoted to auditing and questioning Them (at least a subset) and Their managers about SatisFactory project outcomes and how Their working experience has been enhanced. All these activities will be preparatory both for people training and for the handover of such solutions in production plus, one time more, capitalizing feedback and lessons learned for further dissemination and exploitation.

2.4 INVOLVED ACTORS

As stated multiple times in above chapters, paragraphs and notes, SatisFactory project core is based on user centred design, where user experience forms the basis for (implied / explicit) requirements collection, for design guidance and validation of results. By so, COMAU Use Cases definition, analysis, implementation and test, have been lead in close contact with all Value Chain representative people, which would now benefit form SatisFactory deployment. Working altogether with workers and employees meant enhancing communication, promoting dissemination and awareness, sharing common vision and intents, making everyone feel responsible for common successes and welfare, training and motivation, capitalization of lessons learned, planning and scheduling, ...

Since the whole life cycle of COMAU products and solutions have been covered by SatisFactory implementations, as already stated, involved actors selected among stakeholders, belong to three main clusters:

- Design and Engineering cluster, dealing with machines concepts and drawing generation paying a dramatic attention to the ergonomics in each phase of their useful life (from manufacturing to assembly and commissioning, transportation, operation and maintenance).
- Manufacturing, whose employees are devoted to management and supervising of resources both in house (on premises), during machine development and assembly, and on site, where machines reach their final destination and are re-assembled undergoing commissioning and final testing prior to delivery. Workers that practically perform such activities are obviously part of Manufacturing too.

- Customer Care, i.e. all the people caring of installations value improvement and maintaining during the whole life of COMAU products and solutions.

Relevant figures involved are, respectively, System Engineers, Technical / Manufacturing Leaders, Process Operators and – last but not least – Technical Service Specialists. Such figures have been already described and analysed into SatisFactory Deliverable D1.1 – User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines (in all its various iterations already issued, i.e. D1.1.1, D1.1.2 and D1.1.3), and also in this document (see especially **Paragraph 2.2.2** for what concerns technical service personnel).

Following paragraphs will deal with a brief description of the actors' roles inside COMAU company.

2.4.1 System Engineer

System Engineers are responsible for evaluation and eventual revision (re-engineering) of detailed design of COMAU technical solutions and their integration, in order to guarantee that production engineering requirements stated by customer in project technical specification documents have been fulfilled and ensuring compliance to COMAU internal procedures and standards, to safety and ergonomics regulations not only during machine operation, but even on the WorkPlace of their manufacturing and, after, during the entire life cycle, from maintenance to disposal. Furthermore, They are responsible for certification (CE / international) and Risk Assessment of COMAU technical solutions, again during whole life cycle, plus process simulation. System Engineers are used to manage all aspects related to:

- Machines layout;
- Mechanical drawing;
- Electrical, software and hydraulic / pneumatic schemas;
- Ergonomics and Safety issues;
- Preparation of all documentation that needs to be delivered for manufacturing or, later, to customer for autonomous machine conduction (by so, manuals included);
- Model creation and process simulation.

COMAU System Engineers have been both designers for what concerns ergonomics-related applications (like ISMB ones, with wearable sensors meant to monitor Process Operators trunk bending forward / backward, sideways or twisting), contributing e.g. the appropriate alarm generation and raising rules summarized in **Table 4** and **Table 5** shown shortly above in Chapter 2.3, and would then benefit of relevant implementation to ease their job in identifying possible waste and losses due to eventual unforeseen or out of order un-ergonomic positions.

2.4.2 Manufacturing / Technical Leader

The two figures of Manufacturing and Technical Leader are partially overlapping, especially for what concerns SatisFactory scope and perimeter. They are both indeed responsible for coordinating resources (like Process Operators) at ShopFloor level, in order to carry out activities related to specific projects or mass production of standard products (like COMAU

robots), within scope, time and cost, i.e. under constraints of Customer / internal (in case of standards) specifications, resources availability (men, material, ShopFloor space, tools), project timeline and schedule, budget.

Their role is anyway not overlapping to Project Managers one; They indeed are meant to enforce PM and / or to report directly to Her / Him in case of deviations or issues.

Manufacturing Leaders (MLs) are moreover safety-related topics supervisors or are directly managing ShopFloor supervisors; as monitoring and controlling functions, They deal 360° with short term logistics resources planning (men, material, tools), management and coordination. Furthermore, accordingly to WCM principles, They are responsible for assuring work quality and continuous improvement, both in technical solutions (strong problem solvers) and – especially – in WorkPlace Organization; by so, MLs are interested (and contributed during requirements collection) into (/to) all SatisFactory solutions promoting:

- Human Resources management;
- Process Operators monitoring and supervising, both under an efficiency point of view (like ISMB Supervisor Tool assessing process completion status) and on safety-related topics (see for example again ISMB Supervisor Tool to monitor PPE presence, detect incidents, track intrusions in forbidden zones);
- WorkPlace ergonomics improvement (by so all SatisFactory modules are included, from ISMB ergonomics sensors reading Process Operators trunk bending forward / backward, sideway or twisting, to all REGOLA solutions);
- Human Resources development and training (see REGOLA Creation and Visualization Tools);
- Work organization method assessment.

Technical Leaders (TLs) deal instead more with the technical guidance and leadership of manufacturing resources; They are responsible for planning plus monitoring and controlling (time, cost and scope / quality) in order to ensure technical compliance to project specifications and / or to COMAU company standards (regulations).

They must guarantee requested technical performance from the early stages of preliminary design, to detailed design of machines and manufacturing systems, until final customer acceptance, with Project Manager support and guidance. They are accountable over:

- Technical design of machines and lines with dedicated team;
- Design team coordination;
- Eventual external suppliers management;
- Reporting project progress and ensuring adherence to milestones;
- Interfacing with workers employed in by the ShopFloor.

Furthermore, Technical Leaders deal with Lessons Learned / OPLs capitalization plus cooperate with documentation collection and delivery, by so they are surely involved with REGOLA Creation / Presentation Tools design and validation.

Finally TLs (usually divided into Mechanical and Controls Technical Leaders, whether Their main focus is on mechanical design or electrical, pneumatic and fluidic hardware plus software programming), are expert problem solvers and are used to address production engineering issues.

2.4.3 Process Operator

Process Operators are SatisFactory project main target and stakeholders. Responsible for own WorkPlace cleaning, inspection and maintenance plus working conditions, effectiveness and efficiency improvement, they are definitely end users of most SatisFactory modules and solutions, suggestions collection platforms included (where supervisors, i.e. Manufacturing and Technical Leaders will serve as evaluators).

Process Operators are so-called “Mechatronics” workers, i.e. workers dealing with industrial automation systems manufacturing, with competences ranging from mechanics to controls, i.e. a balanced mix of electrical / pneumatic / fluidic hardware and informatics (software programming, deployment and commissioning). They do follow the entire process into construction of machinery and production systems, from the manufacturing and assembly of single components to integration of entire system, including following tasks:

- Mechanical assembly;
- Electrical wiring;
- Pneumatic / fluidic piping;
- Preliminary and final testing;
- “First-aid” troubleshooting;
- Support to power-up and final delivery to customer (“Commissioning”).

Process Operators are used to work both inside COMAU or on customer premise; they furthermore work in team under coordination of Manufacturing plus Technical Leaders.

2.4.4 After Sales Service Engineer

COMAU Service Engineers, organized per competence centres, i.e. the Business Units they are belonging to (Robotics and Automation Products, Automation Systems or Powertrain Machining), are top skilled, highly experienced engineers with a strong technical background; Their core competences range from analytical and methodological approaches toward troubleshooting and problem solving, to practical on field intervention, both on just measuring plus inspection purposes and consisting of manual repair / parts replacement on the machine.

Service Engineers work at the same time on internal maintaining of COMAU products (e.g. refurbishment or retooling of old products coming back to COMAU premises after useful life expiration) and on supporting local Maintenance teams on customer site. In the latter case, They are both asked to grant Their availability to emergency support calls and to rashly intervene physically on customer premise, potentially out of office hours or during holidays / weekends. This situation classifies this job as a challenging one.

The tasks They are asked to perform are mainly related to:

- Programmed pre-emptive / preventive / periodic professional maintenance activities, accordingly to maintenance calendars and usage & maintenance manuals / procedures (They even support customer and COMAU System Engineers in creating of such documentation and schedules); taking care of COMAU products / solutions (systems) around the world, to maintain and enhance, improve their value during their whole useful life. Usually such tasks are the ones customer is not willing to perform on its own (whether why difficult, requiring challenging and expert judgment /

competences, or simply why they are not structured internally to perform Autonomous Maintenance stuff).

- Emergency intervention in case of machine fault or breakdown that cannot be immediately restored by customer technicians on Their own.
In this case, COMAU Service Engineers are asked to perform troubleshooting by exploding Fault Trees, observing phenomena, analysing direct causes (resolving which production can immediately been restored) and investigating Root Causes whose elimination will solve definitely the issue, preventing fault / breakdown phenomena to happen again.

From these two macro-tasks descriptions, it is easy to understand that the main two branches Service Engineers are used to deal with are 1) procedures creation and maintaining, 2) capitalization of Lessons Learned (on Early Equipment Management⁶ or on-field reuse purposes).

Thus, all SatisFactory components dealing with (maintenance) procedures creation, procedures life-cycle management (update, modification), on-Cloud sharing and maintenance calendars creation and execution management (like REGOLA Creation Tool and Procedures Server, ABE and ISMB Maintenance Technicians schedulers) are of Their immediate and undoubted interest, when working altogether with System Engineers.

Moreover, for a rapid training and competences assessment of new hired people (due to the pauperisation of technical skills, even if it is a background requirement for enrolment into Service Engineers staff), procedural support tools (REGOLA Presentation Tool, GlassUP AR SmartGlasses) will play a crucial role, both during in-house formation and on-the-job, on-customer-site training.

Furthermore, one challenge Service Engineers are asked to face in everyday life, altogether with the need for rapid technical competences growth, is “background asymmetry”, i.e. the difficulty of communicating with people whose technical skills are not as strong as COMAU Service Engineers’ are. These are the main reasons why 1) COMAU service execution is so precious and 2) local presence of COMAU technicians is lot of times required.

Having anyway skilled and experienced resources traveling frequently or even lending Them to customer by leaving a COMAU on-site coverage during or after installations commissioning phase, results in costs, that should be at least partially avoided if a more effective remote support than rush night calls is made available. This is the main motor behind BSC 1.2 Remote Maintenance Support (see relevant chapter, i.e. 2.1.2); the objective is having a remote support consisting into Voice over IP (VoIP) and video real-time streaming in mobility, plus eventually possibility of AR drawing visualization solutions (i.e. COMAU Service Engineers would draw instructions based on video streams coming from the field, that will be shown, in AR indeed on client side). This solution would support both COMAU Service Engineers undergoing on-the-job training without direct physical support of senior ones, and customer Maintenance technicians that will be able to perform simpler tasks on Their own just “tele-guided” remotely from Grugliasco (or whichever COMAU premise). Also

⁶ Early Equipment Management (EEM) is one of World Class Manufacturing (WCM) technical pillars, dealing with an integrated simultaneous engineering (seeing customer and line builders like COMAU working altogether) of automation products or generally industrial productive systems meant to design new technical solutions including improvements coming from ShopFloor capitalized on-field experience indeed.

REGOLA procedures Visualization Tool can support local personnel in performing of maintenance tasks, especially in case standard tutorials are enough to perform the activity and troubleshooting is not required, by so without need for additional remote support.

Finally, suggestions and Lessons Learned capitalization tools will be of Their and entire company interest.

A further, future step for BSC 1.2 Remote Maintenance Support improvement, may be – why not – integration with real-time machine data exchange in order to perform real Condition Based Maintenance (i.e. funded onto machine conditions feedback in output and consequent dynamic schedules and not on fixed calendars), plus Predictive Maintenance.

3. SUNLIGHT USE CASES

3.1 SUNLIGHT BUSINESS SCENARIOS

In this chapter, implementation planning, initial setup and usage of available components on SUNLIGHT Business Scenarios will be described.

SatisFactory components planning and implementation have been organized accordingly to Business Scenarios analysis described in detail into SatisFactory Deliverable D1.2 – Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description.

Business Scenario	Application Scenario	Name
BSC-3		<i>Knowledge-enabled support of systems and workforce for semi-automated battery assembly lines</i>
	BSC 3.1	Preventive and corrective maintenance management system
BSC-4		<i>Monitoring and learning activities at battery production lines</i>
	BSC 4.1	Motive power battery assembly line
	BSC 4.2	Monitoring of cell temperature during jar formation and data collection
	BSC 4.3	Training platform for production process motive power batteries assembly line

Table 6 – List of SUNLIGHT Business Scenarios and Application Scenarios

3.1.1 SUNLIGHT Deployment Areas Presentation

SUNLIGHT premise consists of several ShopFloors, producing a large number of products. Two of them have been selected to deploy scenarios that have been detailed into SatisFactory Deliverable D1.2. The first one is motive power battery assembly line and the second one is jar formation ShopFloor. Following image shows SUNLIGHT plant buildings layout and the exact location of the two involved ShopFloors.

Image 28 – SUNLIGHT factory overview, Business Scenarios related ShopFloors location

On the motive power assembly line, batteries for forklifts are assembled. The entire process is performed manually in six steps. Battery cells are placed into metal battery box accordingly to specifications. The layout depends on battery type, accordingly to relevant drawings available by the ShopFloor.

Image 29 – Motive power batteries assembly line, battery cells placement

Next, cells are connected altogether creating a battery string. The connection pattern depends on battery type. Connection diagrams are available beside assembly line. In following steps battery cells are filled up with electrolyte and sealed by placing sealing caps.

Image 30 – Motive power batteries assembly line

Into jar formation ShopFloor, battery cells are filled up with electrolyte while chargers induce formation charge. Complete cycle duration (Flow Time) is 24 hrs. Critical point in this process is that cell temperature must remain below 50°C. For this reason, the electrolyte is flowing through the cells continuously until the process is finished.

Image 31 – Jar formation ShopFloor

3.1.2 Deployment Activity Plan and Site Preparation

In order to deploy SatisFactory components successfully, an activities schedule has been rolled out and relevant ShopFloor preparation has been carried out. Accurate planning ensures that systems will be installed smoothly, on time and on schedule, without any significant issue. Activity plan has been focused into achieving following specific objectives:

- Define steps, work plan and schedule required to prepare and convert existing application data;
- Define steps and relevant schedule required to install and test hardware and software components;
- Identify facilities and hardware requirements for each component and plan additional components procurement, site arrangements and upgrades;
- Define an alternative plan in the unlikely event that unexpected events may occur which will threaten systems installation failure.

Deployment schedule relies on specific components delivery by technology providing partners, including both hardware and software tools. SUNLIGHT worked altogether with technology providing partners, in order to ensure that deployment schedule would have been realistic for all parties.

3.2 SUNLIGHT INSTALLATION

SUNLIGHT aims within its involvement into SatisFactory project, can be summarized into three objectives.

1. **Production activities real-time support:** smart AR interfaces will provide to workers both an overview of their tasks and activities during Their working day, as well as real-time information on changes regarding Their work, such as components to be used, or modification to the amount of cells to be produced.
2. **Events and incidents logging:** Real-time interaction between actors with different roles (workers, supervisors, technicians, managers) has been explored, alongside with various incidents and events.
3. **Learning environment:** SatisFactory modules learning environment is expected to greatly impact on SUNLIGHT production plants, allowing for fast training of new employees and introduction of the workforce to new technologies.

To achieve above described objectives, in order for SUNLIGHT to improve its production facility, several Use Cases and Scenarios must be taken into account. These scenarios involve installation of all SatisFactory project components and their testing plus validation both individually and altogether as a whole.

Installation of most of the components has been already performed. CERTH installed its CIDEM tool, AR In-Factory, Incident Detection, Collaboration and Gamification platforms plus the sensors required for Smart Sensor Network implementation (i.e. depth cameras and thermal camera). ISMB performed installation of its Smart Assembly Station solution, Notification Panel and Gesture & Content Recognition Manager plus Localization Manager components of Context Aware Manager toolkit. Atlantis deployed its Maintenance Toolkit, iDSS and implemented the connection of iDSS with other SatisFactory components. Finally,

FIT installed LinkSmart Middleware connecting all Satisfactory components altogether. All deployed tools details are exploded in following paragraphs, one per each component.

3.2.1 *Ontology Manager Design and Implementation*

Satisfactory Ontology Manager (OM) is designed upon the hourglass-shaped ontological structure (see **Image 32**), called Satisfactory Ontology (SFO). The bridging element, i.e. the Satisfactory Ontology OWL class, plus the first level subclasses, aims to provide a shared vocabulary through which semantic data, mostly regarding Assets, Procedures and Workers, can be gathered within a knowledge base. This shared vocabulary is used as a link between domain-specific ontologies (ShopFloor oriented semantic structures) and CIDEM data-oriented ontologies at the very lowest level. The three ShopFloor-oriented ontologies (COMAU, SUNLIGHT, and CERTH) aim at representing the knowledge that is related to each specific industrial partner and relevant Business Scenarios (BSCs), taking into account specific terms and elements that can be leveraged to manage and optimize Human Resources. Finally, other low-granularity models contain ShopFloor data-oriented ontologies, which have been derived from Satisfactory Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM) schemas; hence, it aims at supporting the semantic enrichment of CIDEM XML data.

Image 32 – Satisfactory Ontology (SFO) high level structure

Satisfactory Ontology Manager has been integrated into Satisfactory Framework through Open Source software, named Open Semantic Framework (OSF). This allows for deployment of Satisfactory Ontology (SFO) and provides a mean both for managing knowledge base and to carry out semantics-driven analysis.

Located at CERTH premises, the OSF Server is an Ubuntu VM that has following hardware / software specifications:

CPU	Dual-Core
Architecture	64-bit
Operating System	Ubuntu 14.04
PHP version	PHP 5.6
Drush version	Drush 8.0
Disk type	SATA
Internet access	Yes
Web browser & version	Firefox Chrome
Access	Team Viewer 10

Table 7 – OSF Server VM implementation specification details

3.2.2 Semantics-Based ShopFloor Information Management

The Ontology Manager (OM) aims to utilise information stored in CIDEM, mostly B2MML-based static and dynamic data, and to transform it into RDF / XML (Resource Description Framework) triplets by employing Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformation (XSLT) as a mean to map XML and OWL elements, and to execute the actual data transformation (Image 33).

Image 33 – From XML to RDF

SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language) can be therefore exploited to express queries across the obtained RDF data sources, enabling a semantics-enhanced Human Resources (HR) information browsing and knowledge management. Here, the challenge was to integrate data from multiple production cells and / or lines, to account for different types of actors and operators (also in terms of skills and organizational level), to consider different levels of expertise of employees, to combine information from the localization system of the employees in the ShopFloor, and to integrate with the solution package suitable for the execution of a certain task.

As a result of the interaction, Satisfactory Decision Support System (DSS), Ontology Manager (or Semantic Manager) may infer the time for each worker to perform a desired job. Based on the evaluation step, for all next steps the outcome is evaluated by the DSS through a HR optimisation process that leads to an improved workload balancing as can be seen in **Image 34**.

Image 34 – Data exchange flow at SUNLIGHT SA ShopFloor

The efficient management of Human Resources and the optimization of workers allocation accordingly to the needs of an organization, are extremely important in fulfilling both organization objectives and workers feeling of satisfaction. Semantically-enriched information produced by proposed framework, can be exploited in different application scenarios. Furthermore, availability of automatically generated semantic information about HR and tasks, paves the way towards automated actions or suggestions for actions regarding the assignments of tasks. This benefit can be important in highly dynamic environments, where, for example, new maintenance operations can occur, due to unexpected critical machine failures, and immediate response to handle the malfunction by the appropriate personnel is required. Another practical application of the produced semantically-enriched information is its presentation to the HR supervisor in a user-friendly, human-readable format, in order to provide useful insights about the performance of workers, Their skills and Their progress (D. Arena et al., 2017).

The Ontology Manager itself provides the functionalities described, however, these can be further exploited to enable the Satisfactory decision-making engine performing the following indicative operations:

1. Propose the most suitable worker to perform a new arriving task;

2. Use historical semantic data to carry out real-time intelligent decisions and schedule new tasks based on multiple criteria;
3. Balance the workload among workers efficiently by taking into account Their skills and the characteristics of the scheduled tasks.

3.2.3 Gamification Framework – Gamification-Based Tools

The Gamification Framework is a central framework used to manage all gamification initiatives to be implemented inside the factory. This means that Gamification Framework provides certain APIs to external systems, e.g. Suggestions Platform, in order to enable those to create games, add tasks to these games and allocate points to these tasks. Gamification Framework consists of a database containing all data related to all games created by all external systems utilizing Gamification Framework itself. Cumulative scores are communicated to workers via the Digital Screen, while individual points are communicated via the Social Collaboration Platform.

3.2.4 Gamification Framework – AIMMS App – Gamification-Based Tools

AIMMS App included into SatisFactory project Gamification Platform, consists of Apps meant for different kind of actors.

Workers' scores can be seen into AIMMS games of Gamification Platform. The App is designed so that, when a worker joins the game, She / He earns different amount of points for each performed task. If a worker starts a task, She / He gains 5 points. When They end a task, They gain 15 points and when They comment-in one task they gain 10 points. This scoring system was agreed altogether with the end user, i.e. SUNLIGHT, in order to account for their business strategy. It has to be underlined that points allocation is a parameter that can be configured accordingly to priorities set by end user.

Image 35 – Social Collaboration Platform with Gamification Tools

Above screenshot shows, among other things, how a worker joins a game. Before someone joins the game, Her / His score is deactivated and, after joining, the points are shown on the screen. Workers do not gain points by simply joining a game. They should create, comment or end a task to earn points.

When a task is created on the online application by a worker, one dedicated service can detect the creation of such task. Then, Gamification Framework stays working in background in order to award points to worker accordingly to created tasks number. Gamification Application running in console mode is shown below.

Image 36 – Gamification Framework running in background

In order the Gamification Framework to work, there should be a connection to AIMMS Application already installed on premises or to Cloud-based applications. For SUNLIGHT installation, AIMMS Application has been installed locally; BASE_URL and AIMMS_Services_URL are given in table below.

[services]	URL
idss_bind_url	http://10.1.7.136:9070/
aimms_service	http://atlas.sunlight.gr:35004/
gamification_service	http://localhost:8037

Table 8 – AIMMS Application services URLs⁷

The idss_bind_url is the basic URL used for internal iDSS installation at SUNLIGHT. aims_service URL is instead used for invoking AIMMS services on which the basic installation relies on. Finally, gamification_service URL is the one connecting AIMMS Application, through iDSS, with Gamification API.

⁷ Please note urls may change due to technical needs

Image 37 shows that connection between all components has been successfully established. Further steps needed for Gamification Framework and participation into AIMMS App games are:

1. A new task must be created. The new task can be seen by iDSS and contains all necessary information about it.
2. The new task must be initiated. iDSS is able to understand which user is responsible for this task, how many points should be assigned, since different actions lead to different scores, and is finally able to communicate the score to Social Collaboration Platform.
3. The points gained starting a new task have been assigned. A new task yield 5 points. These points are assigned to all actors, since, when the task is created, the worker who created the task itself is used to belong to a specific team and also to “All Actors”. As a result, both teams and workers participating to, do receive the points for starting a new task.
4. Logging into Social Collaboration Platform, everyone can check the points capitalized into each game. If someone participates to the game, her / his points will be available too, even if they decide to leave the game for a certain time period. This happens because workers do not always work in the same position, and different positions require different games while some positions have no relevant game.


```

C:\idss - idss -- gamification
Total tasks:1386-last task 131017-last completed 131017
^C
C:\Atlantis\idSSWithGF>
C:\Atlantis\idSSWithGF>--gamification
'--gamification' is not recognized as an internal or external command,
operable program or batch file.
C:\Atlantis\idSSWithGF>idss -- gamification
2017-02-03 14:32:11,718 [1] DEBUG ABE.IDSS.Program [<null>] - starting
Last task :131017
^C
C:\Atlantis\idSSWithGF>idss -- gamification
2017-02-03 14:51:54,845 [1] DEBUG ABE.IDSS.Program [<null>] - starting
Last task :131017
Total tasks:1386-last task 131017-last completed 131017
Total tasks:1386-last task 131017-last completed 131017
New Task 131026 @ 3 ISAD - Daily check actions 25040
send start action <15> for game AIMMS
<"result": "OK">
Total tasks:1387-last task 131026-last completed 131017
  
```

Image 37 – New Task Started into AIMMS App Game – view from console

Into above figure, a view of iDSS console application is shown. In this view, the new task can be seen, as well as worker who created it. iDSS application is able to recognise worker responsible for the task, it can notify Social Collaboration Platform and assign corresponding points to workers. Points are assigned for starting, completing and commenting a certain task.

Finally, scores can be seen into Social Collaboration Platform. For starting a task, 5 points are appointed to the worker who started it. For commenting-on a task, 10 points are yielded and for finishing a task 15 points can be gained.

Image 38 – Social Collaboration Platform

3.2.5 Training Data Analytics Tool

Training Toolkit is part of the On-the-Job Training Toolkit. KPIs can be created using Training Toolkit, while already existing KPIs can be selected to be used, accordingly to business objectives of every installation. Training Data Analytics Tool is still into its development phase and will be deployed on SUNLIGHT premises as soon as the development itself will be completed.

3.3 BSC 3.1 – PREVENTIVE AND CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

SUNLIGHT ShopFloor production lines operates 24/7. Due to this tight schedule, the avoidance of malfunctions is crucial; it is also important all the heterogeneous operations are performed as smoothly as possible. A Technical / Maintenance Team is responsible for maintaining machinery and equipment. BSC 3.1 goal is to organize Maintenance activities effectively and to improve Technical Department working environment.

Image 39 – BSC 3.1 implementation Gantt Chart

In order BSC 3.1 to be fully implemented, various SatisFactory components need to be used. Many of them have already been installed while some of them are still pending, accordingly to BSC 3.1 Gantt-Chart depicted into **Image 39**.

Application scenario can be described by following steps:

- Failure event notification;
- Action planning;
- Work scheduling;
- Tasks assignment;
- Work execution;
- Work completion;
- Production of intervention reports.

3.3.1 A Brief Description of BSC 3.1 Steps Already Covered

3.3.1.1 Failure Event Notification

BSC-3.1 scenario starts at the time Maintenance Manager receives notification of Maintenance intervention is needed. The source of information may be one of Maintenance Manager supervisors, e.g. Production Plant Manager or Production Planner, iDSS or Smart Sensor Network.

In each case the information follows a different path before it reaches the Maintenance Manager.

Case 1: information provided by a Supervisor

In this case, SatisFactory platform is not involved directly but it could have been used from Supervisors before Their contact with Maintenance Manager.

Case 2: information provided by iDSS

iDSS is a component acting like decision centre. DSS refers to Decision Support System. iDSS gets info from Smart Sensor Network, CIDEM and Ontology Manager. After processing this information, it provides feedback to decision makers regarding immediate actions to be performed in response to ShopFloor-level incidents, altogether with changes to manufacturing operations and processes, and also maintenance operations and schedules.

In BSC 3.1 Maintenance Manager may be informed by iDSS about maintenance operations and relevant schedules for each machine. Furthermore, Maintenance Manager can be informed of current machinery status. However, in order the information from iDSS to be easily understood, other components is needed on visualization purpose. Components that can visualize this information are AR in-Factory Platform with Visualization Tools, Gamification Framework with Gamification App API, Multi Modal & Augmented HMIs with GUI component. Each of these components is able to visualize different kind of information, in various ways and by mean of different kinds of devices like tables, AR glasses, etc.

Case 3: information came from Smart Sensor Network

Smart Sensor Network (SSN) consists of a set of devices allowing the interaction between physical world and SatisFactory platform. Moreover, it is equipped with a robust communication module for IoT enabled devices communications. The SSN is able to communicate with Middleware. The connection with this middleware allows the SSN to visualize information it provides, through components which can visualize it, like iDSS.

As soon as Maintenance Manager receives the information about the need for maintenance intervention through either of the above ways, the first step has been fulfilled. Then, Maintenance Manager continues to next step, i.e. action planning.

3.3.1.2 Action Planning

In the second step, Maintenance Manager prioritizes open issues. In this step, once more iDSS is able to help Maintenance Manager getting information from CIDEM and Ontology. CIDEM and Ontology can provide the appropriate data and “opinion”, respectively, so that iDSS should help Maintenance Manager getting to efficient decisions. Furthermore, through Visualization Tools and Middleware, Maintenance Manager may access CIDEM acquiring information about the availability of spare parts, tools and manpower, in order to design an Action Plan.

As far as Maintenance Manager has all needed information from SatisFactory tools, it will be possible stepping over to Work Scheduling.

3.3.1.3 Work Scheduling and Task Assignment

Since the Action Planning has been performed, the next step for Maintenance Manager is assigning the work to Technicians, accordingly to the Action Plan itself. Technicians are equipped with tablets, smartphones or AR glasses. All these devices are connected to SatisFactory platform in real-time.

Once Maintenance Manager has sent the assignments to Technicians, it is time for Technicians to perform relevant activities.

3.3.1.4 Work Execution

As mentioned before, each technician is equipped with tablet, mobile phone or AR glasses. Through these devices, technicians are able to communicate with each other. While the work is being executed, according to given instructions, any unexpected difficulty can be reported to the Manager for additional advises. Real-time communication is provided by Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence component. Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence component, combined with Collaborative Tool component, can provide visual communication among Maintenance / Technical Team members, in order to exchange knowledge in real-time. Information exchanged during work execution, can be store into one repository. Stored incidents may be useful in the future for novice technicians to gain experience in real situations that took place in the past and may be repeated in the future (Lessons Learned).

When maintenance work has been completed, technicians proceed to next step, i.e. Work Completion phase.

3.3.1.5 Work Completion

When the work has been completed, related SatisFactory components must be informed. Especially, iDSS must be real-time updated about everything that concerns available resources, like spare parts, tools, manpower, etc. As a result, it is very important that, after work has been completed, SatisFactory modules will be updated. Update of SatisFactory components is performed in CIDEM and Ontology throughout Visualization Tools and Middleware, and, consequently, into iDSS.

As soon as SatisFactory system has been informed that maintenance work has been completed, Technicians and all the other resources involved change Their status and Intergraded DSS may suggest Them for other activities.

3.3.1.6 Production of Intervention Reports

Finally, the last step is production of intervention reports. Maintenance Manager creates a report, providing a detailed description of actions undertaken. These details are stored into CIDEM and relevant information is made available online, mainly to Technicians and to Maintenance Manager, for future use. The reports also help iDSS and Ontology to provide more reliable suggestions.

3.3.2 Satisfactory Components Selected for BSC 3.1

In this paragraph, components used in BSC 3.1 are described.

3.3.2.1 Integrated DSS (iDSS)

iDSS is a multi-layered system that can integrate many sources of information and data, as well as communicate with many components of SatisFactory project. SUNLIGHT deployment has connections with all installed components. These connections were tested sending signals to and listening signals receipt from iDSS, in order to check connectivity has been established and prevent issues would arise during the implementation of further components on SUNLIGHT premises.

3.3.2.2 Human Resources Workload Balancing

Usually, tasks are assigned at the beginning of each working day, and this schedule should be followed throughout the whole day. The HR Workload Balancing Toolkit provides an automated way to schedule work tasks, and it schedules the tasks in order to achieve maximum efficiency. Each task is assigned to one or more workers, accordingly to different criteria which apply for the task. The toolkit finds the most suitable solution for every type of task and creates the daily schedule. Though automation through the toolkit is an improvement to the overall scheduling process, there are always exemptions, which should be dealt with. The most common deviations from the schedule happen when there is a machine malfunction and production cannot continue without first fixing the problem.

iDSS installation into SUNLIGHT ShopFloor deals with aforementioned problems. An automated schedule has been implemented in order to more efficiently solve the re-adaptation of work schedules due to various reasons.

The Human Resources Work Balance Toolkit of the iDSS needs a connection with Maintenance Toolkit, LinkSmart Middleware and CIDEM to work properly. Signals are sent and received from each Satisfactory component which create the data needed by other components. The BASE_URL and the SERVICES_URL of the Maintenance Toolkit, mentioned into Gamification components related chapters, have been used here too.

The re-adaptation of work schedule can be achieved in two steps of daily scheduling process. The first is initial scheduling and the second step is scheduling of inferred tasks during working day. Initial scheduling can be done using Maintenance Toolkit and relevant tasks can be seen into Maintenance Toolkit Calendar View.

Image 40 – Initial scheduling into Maintenance Toolkit Calendar View

Selected task is shown by a yellow box in the appropriate day of the calendar view, while worker to whom task has been appointed, is highlighted in green. Tasks can be ranked with many different criteria and, depending on these criteria, they are displayed accordingly into the calendar. Human Resources Work Balance Toolkit works following below steps:

1. New tasks are created into Maintenance Toolkit and iDSS detects them.
2. A new task arrives during the working day. Human Resources Work Balance Toolkit evaluates it accordingly to criteria and rules set by iDSS;
3. Worker daily agenda and time needed for new task, as long as other criteria are evaluated by iDSS; new tasks are prioritised accordingly to iDSS rules.
4. Once iDSS has evaluated the tasks, it inserts them into the work schedule accordingly to the prioritisation that has been made.
5. The tasks are re-arranged by iDSS and shown into Maintenance Toolkit calendar view.

Image 41 – Rescheduling of five new tasks through iDSS

Image 41 shows five new tasks which have been created into the Maintenance Toolkit and detected by iDSS. iDSS prioritized them first and then schedules them in the appropriate way, accordingly to rules and criteria. Rescheduled tasks can be shown into Maintenance Toolkit calendar, alongside with all already existing tasks and trigger the re-adaptation of work schedule.

Image 42 – Placeholder

3.3.2.3 Context-Aware Manager – Multiple Media Manager

Multiple-Media Manager goal is to provide a reliable distribution infrastructure for video streams from heterogeneous sources and being able to store them into a central unit.

3.3.2.4 AR in-Factory Platform

The services that AR in-Factory Platform provides can be split in two groups. Services of the first group support employees while performing specific Operating Procedures (OPs) and can range from instructions for maintenance interventions to assembly of a machine. The second group comprehends services meant for creating an interactive and visual communication between the worker and SatisFactory platform. The AR in-Factory Platform includes end-use applications for creation of operative procedures and for their interactive visualization. Finally, it supports devices like AR glasses, smartphones and tablets.

Image 43 – AR in-Factory Platform components diagram

Sub-components of AR in-Factory Platform are listed below.

- **AR OP Visualization Tool (Mobile Version):** this Visualization Tool provides a rich set of possible visualizations and interaction functionalities, in order to present previously prepared AR OP directly “on-the-job”. Operators can choose the level of detail and the kind of information They need. Visualization Tool can be installed onto various devices like, tablets, smartphones, etc. and in plenty presentation modes (e.g. Virtual Reality, text only, hybrid).
- **AR OP Visualization Tool (GlassUP Version):** this version of Visualization Tool provides porting of above discussed mobile version to GlassUP wearable devices.

- **AR OP Creation Tool:** Creation Tool is software that converts scenarios for training or production environment procedures in a format compatible with AR OP Visualization Tool.
- **AR OP “On-the-Job” Creation Tool:** This tool can be used like AR OP Creation Tool but has the ability to manage data and information directly captured from the work environment at runtime. Data come from sensors populating Smart Sensor Network.

3.3.2.5 Multi Modal & Augmented HMIs and AR Devices

Mobile devices connected to SatisFactory through Middleware such as tablets, smartphones and AR glasses are able to visualize digital data.

Image 44 – GlassUP industrial AR glasses prototype

3.4 BSC 4 – MONITORING AND LEARNING ACTIVITIES ON BATTERY PRODUCTION LINES

BSC 4 takes place on battery production lines. It consists of three scenarios; each of them has different purpose and goals. The three scenarios are:

- BSC 4.1 – Motive power battery assembly line;
- BSC 4.2 – Monitoring of cell temperature during jar formation plus data collection;
- BSC-4.3 – Training platform for production process on motive power batteries assembly line.

3.5 BSC 4.1 – MOTIVE POWER BATTERY ASSEMBLY LINE

First Business Scenario takes place into assembly line for motive power batteries. Once battery cells have been produced, into another SUNLIGHT factory department, next steps involve (i) packing cells into metallic boxes, (ii) connect cells altogether creating a battery string, (iii) installing terminal plugs and water filling system (optional), (iv) checking the need for additional electrolyte, (iv) passing from quality check and (v) putting labels, packing and forwarding to warehouse for dispatch.

Image 45 – BSC 4.1 implementation Gantt Chart

The aforementioned production line does not use machineries and almost in every step the procedure is done by hand. If a worker is new, or wants further information about a procedure in the assembly line, She / He may find what She / He needs thanks to the Smart Assembly Station. Information on every procedure and manuals are easily accessible. Access to information needed, can be done remotely to Smart Assembly Station engine through the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager component of Context-Aware Manager. Moreover, when using mobile devices like tablets, smartphones or AR googles, workers can have access to required information via LinkSmart Middleware.

In each of above steps, SatisFactory components are going to be used in order for the scenario to achieve its goals. Into next paragraphs, a detailed description of how SatisFactory system is involved.

3.5.1 SatisFactory Components Specified for BSC 4.1

Below the components that were used in BSC 4.1 will be described in details.

3.5.1.1 Smart Assembly Station by ISMB

The Smart Assembly Station by ISMB has been installed in SUNLIGHT ShopFloor.

Image 46 – ISMB Smart Assembly Station installation process

Image 47 – ISMB Smart Assembly Station operating screenshots

3.5.1.2 Installation of components by CERTH

In BSC 4.1, appropriate equipment was installed on SUNLIGHT premises by CERTH too. Installed components are CIDEM, AR in-Factory Platform, Incident Detection, Collaboration Platform, Gamification Platform and sensor from the Smart Sensor Network (depth cameras). Different positions for cameras were tested, prior to selecting final (best) ones, inside battery assembly line area.

Image 48 – Testing and final positioning of depth cameras

After depth cameras have been finally placed and calibrated, they automatically connected via Context Aware Manager component.

Image 49 – Calibration of depth cameras

Finally, testing of components in their whole has been performed.

Image 50 – Testing CERTH installations

3.5.1.3 Smart Sensor Network – UWB Localization Devices – Depth Sensor Network

In order to track workers into the ShopFloor, UWB Localization Devices have been placed. UWB Localization Devices may be tags, anchor nodes or gateways. Tags are placed on workers and anchors to fixed points. This mini-network of devices is able to locate each worker and, cooperating with depth camera, the system is able to check if each worker wears its safety gears (PPE – Personal Protection Equipment), if any worker has fallen or is even able to prevent collisions. Collisions prevention is important due to coexistence of workers who move with forklifts and workers who are used to walk.

3.5.1.4 Context-Aware Manager

Localization Manager

Localization Manager tracks workers and helps them to avoid dangerous or forbidden areas by warning signals (alarms). Furthermore, it supplies knowledge-based information to SatisFactory platform and receives information from UWB Localization Devices through LinkSmart Middleware.

Gesture & Content Recognition Manager

Gesture & Content Recognition subcomponent gets input from a composite RGB and time-of-flight sensor. By processing these inputs, it can detect presence of workers, count them, check if workers do wear their own safety equipment, check if a worker has fallen and at last it can detect gestures.

Gestures detection can be used to control wall screens from distance. For example, a worker may need some info about a procedure. She / He will then be able to open files or change pages by moving Her / His hands.

3.5.1.5 AR in-Factory Platform

In this application workers can benefit from assembly line procedures through Their tablets or mobile phones, with AR SOP Presentation Tools. At each assembly line step there are tags that can be read by tablets of smartphones cameras, and present relevant procedure associated.

Image 51 – AR SOP Presentation Tools at SUNLIGHT battery assembly station

3.6 BSC 4.2 – MONITORING OF CELL TEMPERATURE DURING JAR FORMATION AND DATA COLLECTION

The second Business Scenario, BSC 4.2, has the goal to remotely and continuously monitor the temperature of battery cells during jar formation. Furthermore, it aims to collection and analysis of temperature data. There are 11 jar formation modules covering an area of 1000 m². Now, temperature is measured manually applying a sampling rate of one measurement per hour. Workers that record the temperature are scanning battery cells undergoing formation process one by one. In BSC 4.2 a thermal camera has been installed in order to monitor cells temperature continuously and, as a result, more reliably. Main scope of SatisFactory in BSC 4.2 is to make this procedure more automated and easier for SUNLIGHT workers plus save men hours and effort.

Image 52 – BSC-4.2 implementation Gantt-Chart

The main logical flow of BSC 4.2 – monitoring of cell temperature during jar formation and data collection is:

- Identification of condition-based preventive action;
- Alarm recognition;
- Alarm acknowledgment;
- Work assignment;
- Work execution;
- Work completion;
- Production of intervention reports.

3.6.1 A Brief Description of BSC 4.2 Steps Already Covered

In order to be accomplished, each of the steps that were mentioned into main flow requires certain components of SatisFactory to be implemented. Into following paragraphs, how each step was addressed during application deployment will be explained in detail.

3.6.1.1 Normal Operation

As far as the thermal camera is installed, it will be able to monitor the cells. Thermal cameras belong to Smart Sensor Network component. Smart Sensor Network is connected to Middleware and through the Middleware thermal camera data arrive to Context-Aware Manager component. Context-Aware Manager component is able to process data from thermal camera. The results of Context-Aware component may be visualized and displayed on smartphones, tablets, wall screens or AR glasses. Components that can show information onto an HMI are AR in-Factory Platform with Visualization Tools, Gamification Framework with Gamification App API, Multi Modal & Augmented HMIs with GUI component and Re-Adaptation Toolkit.

3.6.1.2 Identification of Abnormal Situation

During normal duty cycles an abnormal situation may occur, when cell temperature rises over the limit threshold, or when data analysis shows a trend anticipating an overheating of the cell is going to happen during jar formation process.

While thermal camera is monitoring, data are being analyzed by Context-Aware Manager component. So, abnormal situations may be perceived or even predicted!

If an abnormal situation is perceived or predicted, Production Supervisor who is in charge for current shift must be notified.

3.6.1.3 Alarm Recognition

After an abnormal situation has been recognized, the system provides a real-time alarm to Production Supervisor who is in charge in each shift. This alarm will appear on an HMI device that could be a smartphone, tablet, AR glasses or wall screen.

3.6.1.4 Alarm Acknowledgment

Production Supervisor acknowledges the alarm through Her / His tablet and requests for more information. SatisFactory system will provide jar formation module identification number or / and thermal camera that spot the issue. By receiving this information, the exact location of potential incident will be univocally determined.

Additional information such as action plan and working instructions will be available on the screen.

Remaining steps (Work Assignment, Work Execution, Work Completion and Production of Intervention Reports) are performed in same way as relevant steps described for BSC 3.1 (see subchapter into paragraph 3.3.1).

3.6.2 Satisfactory Components Selected for BSC 4.2

3.6.2.1 Smart Sensor Network – Thermal Sensor Network

Thermal Sensor Network constantly monitors the temperature during jar formation. For this scenario two thermal cameras have been installed. The outputs of these cameras can be a color or grayscale image; the value of each pixel corresponds to a temperature. The image is being analyzed in order to recognize incidents due to overheating.

Image 53 – Thermal cameras

3.6.2.2 Integrated DSS – Incident Management Tool

Sensors and thermal cameras monitoring is undertaken by Incident Management Tool of iDSS. This tool is able to primarily provide an on-time warning of a possible abnormal situation and also to predict abnormal situations that still have to come. Furthermore, it will provide appropriate warnings and notifications to ShopFloor Supervisor through different applications and interfaces that are subscribed to CIDEM, including Social and Collaboration Platform.

Image 54 – Satisfactory Incident Detection Engine

3.7 BSC 4.3 – TRAINING PLATFORM FOR PRODUCTION PROCESS ON MOTIVE POWER BATTERIES ASSEMBLY LINE

Application Scenario BSC 4.3 refers to the need of a training platform which will help the trainees to understand how to perform Their job safely and more efficiently. This procedure includes two parts. The first one concerns the theoretical approach that will provide to trainees needed background on each particular process. In the second part, trainees will receive work training which will incorporate also AR tools, making the process more attractive to the trainees. The platform will also include a trainee evaluation questionnaire which will evaluate whether the trainee has been trained sufficiently or not. BSC 4.3 goal is to develop a training platform to demonstrate production processes to the trainees. To achieve this goal, Augmented Reality platform and devices will be used. Moreover, Satisfactory,

through Gamification Framework components, allows trainees and trainers for enriching training material.

Image 55 – BSC-4.3 Implementation Gantt Chart

BSC 4.3 – training platform for production process on motive power batteries assembly line main operational flow is:

- Identification of training needs;
- Determination of training perimeter;
- Training delivery;
- Training feedback;
- Training on the WorkPlace;
- Provision of training material.

3.7.1 Satisfactory Components Selected for BSC 4.3

3.7.1.1 Installation of Components by CERTH

On BSC 4.3 purpose, appropriate equipment has been installed into the ShopFloor also by CERTH. Components that have been installed inside BSC 4.3 perimeter are CIDEM, AR in-Factory Platform, Collaboration Platform and Gamification Platform.

Image 56 – BSC 4.3 installation process (performed by CERTH)

CONCLUSIONS

The present document is a Deliverable of SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under Its Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (H2020).

The just read pamphlet represent furthermore the first iteration of the above mentioned SatisFactory project Deliverable, D5.4.1.

ShopFloor conditions have been presented, analyzed, assessed, both in COMAU and SUNLIGHT. People have been observed during Their working lives and involved into requirements collection and design phase (World Class Manufacturing, Design Thinking and other user-centered approaches). Solutions have been developed and – partially – implemented. First feedback has been collected from the field, stakeholders have been presented and They have / will be interviewed.

A first but still pretty clear overview of SatisFactory living technology on industrial ShopFloors (after lab implementations) has been depicted.

Next months will oversee industrious integration of first Lessons Learned collection, further developments and implementations, final validation.

All these aspects will be collected as an addendum to this document, into second and final iteration of this SatisFactory Deliverable, i.e. D5.4.2 that will be due to Month M36, by Project End Milestone.

In faith, the Authors.

ANNEX 1 – ADDENDUM TO COMAU BSC1.3 – REMOTE MAINTENANCE SUPPORT

During last remote SatisFactory Plenary Meeting (held on Friday June, 9th 2017), one more detailed planning for BSC1.3 implementation has been presented.

By so, this short addendum has been added into Deliverable D5.4.1 annexes.

Image 59 – BSC 1.3 Remote Maintenance Support general architecture draft overview

Here below, the usage scenarios have been described using the storyboard technique, where each step of user experience is described as a scene of a film.

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Scene	Action
Planned maintenance schedule	One Junior After Sales Service Engineer receives, on Her / His tablet , the notification that a periodic, pre-emptive maintenance intervention (scheduled on Her / His calendar) should be performed soon on one robot control cabinet located on COMAU customer premise.
Junior technician training	If needed and not yet performed, the young, less skilled technician can undergo a training period for specific maintenance task, altogether with Her / His supervisor (Senior After Sales Service Engineer), thanks to multi-media platform installed and running on Her / His tablet or on a Windows PC installed in COMAU on training purpose.
Business trip	Then the trained Junior After Sales Service Engineer reaches for COMAU customer premise where the activity should be led.
In-factory multi-media maintenance procedures	The Junior After Sales Service Engineer starts performing the maintenance task, supported by guided procedures created for Her / Him by System Engineers in cooperation with Senior After Sales Service Engineers , through the same multi-media platform used during offline training, but this time in “production mode”. This will even help Her / Him to undergo a bit more of training on the job .
Remote support call	Whether the Junior After Sales Service Engineer should find some issues in performing the intervention, She / He can start a call to Her / His supervisor (Senior After Sales Service Engineer). The call will be enhanced by real-time streaming both of audio and video (video-call) and the possibility of taking pictures and share them with remote supporter.
Remote support with AR	If feasible and coherent with SatisFactory project timing, potentially a further functionality could be implemented, allowing Senior After Sales Service Engineer drawing onto Her / His screen suggestions and instructions that would be streamed to Junior technician tablet and displayed in AR over what She / He is seeing through tablet camera.
Lessons Learned capitalization	Finally, if Suggestion Platform would be deployed on Junior After Sales Service Engineer, She / He can add crucial Lessons Learned gathered during the intervention.
SOPs creation	Such suggestions would be evaluated altogether by COMAU System Engineers and Senior After Sales Service Engineers in order to improve, enhance and expand usage and maintenance manuals / procedures.

Table 9 – BSC 1.3 Storyboard

To reach such an ambitious goal or at least the most relevant parts of it, following Partners’ modules (see **Table 10** below) should be involved and – by so – implemented if not already done.

Partner	Module	Status ⁸	Notes
ABE	AIMMS Portal	Ongoing	Allows System Engineers and Senior After Sales Service Engineers for automation assets management, technical resources administration and pre-emptive maintenance calendars creation and updating.
	AIMMS Mobile App	Ongoing	Allows After Sales Service Engineers to check their work schedule and be aware in advance of needs for planned maintenance interventions, potentially on customer premise.
CERTH	Objects Recognition System (ORS)	Feasibility still to be evaluated	<p>Requiring high computational performances, will probably not fit remote maintenance support usage scenario, especially when on customer premise, due to high latencies over the network.</p> <p>Furthermore, the client has been developed for Windows OS devices, so would not be deployable on Android tablets, now dominating the market.</p> <p>Anyway, whether time will be enough to implement such “nice to have”, can be used to support Junior After Sales Service Engineers’ training in COMAU, with client running on a Windows OS PC equipped with one webcam.</p>
FRAUNHOFER	Suggestions Platform	Feasibility still to be evaluated	<p>Running on a tablet, the same After Sales Service Engineers will be equipped with when working on customer premise, Suggestions Platform will allow them for Lessons Learned capitalization.</p> <p>Suggestions collected in such a way, will be evaluated then by both Senior Service Engineers, acting as supervisors of Junior ones, and System Engineers altogether.</p>

⁸ Data updated on M30 (June 2017).

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GlassUP	AR Smart Glasses	Feasibility still to be evaluated	<p>Smart Glasses can be a valid alternative to a tablet on instructions visualization in AR purpose and on remote support (video-call) purpose too.</p> <p>The big advantage with respect to tablets is that they do not require for Workers' hands encumbrance.</p> <p>The drawback of fatiguing eyes, is minimized by the reduced amount of time they should be worn for.</p> <p>Instructions would come from REGOLA Presentation Tool, which should then be integrated with the googles.</p>
REGOLA	Training Platform	Complete ⁹	<p>Training Platform, made up by Creation Tool and Presentation Tool, allows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• On one side System Engineers altogether with Senior After Sales Service Engineers, to create / update standard pre-emptive and periodic maintenance procedures;• On the other one, Junior Service Engineers to be trained when in COMAU on the procedures They will be asked to perform on customer premise on their own. <p>As mentioned above, Presentation Tool should be integrated with GlassUp AR Glasses, whether implemented.</p>

⁹ Activities already completed for BSC 1.1 – Robot Wrist Assembly. Ad-hoc procedures for maintenance operations / interventions should be created.

	In-Factory Platform	Complete ¹⁰	<p>Performs same functionalities as Training Platform, but allows to exploit procedures when really working online on production equipment.</p> <p>In this case, the Procedures Server is the feature letting maintenance technicians to both download locally on Their tablets relevant procedures prior to start Their business trip, and to access directly the procedures on customer premise whether something has been updated in the meanwhile (sort of procedures Cloud).</p> <p>Finally, as mentioned above, Presentation Tool should be integrated with GlassUp AR Glasses, whether implemented.</p>
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Table 10 – BSC 1.3 Remote Maintenance Support involved Technical Partners modules

Last but not least, something already discussed with REGOLA Partner. As feedback directly coming from maintenance technicians, SatisFactory could take into account the possibility of developing (maybe just applying something already invented into adjacent markets) some kind of equipment to create what in the schema above (**Image 59**) has been defined as “Hands-Free Tablet”.

This means allowing for tablet usage and AR procedures exploitation through REGOLA Visualization Tool, without encumbering After Sales Service Engineers hands when they are both needed on intervention purpose.

¹⁰ Activities already completed for BSC 1.1 – Robot Wrist Assembly. Ad-hoc procedures for maintenance operations / interventions should be created.